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Etymology of American reptile genera

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Abstract

Here we provide the etymologies of all 416 extant reptile genera that occur on the American supercontinent, ranging from Canada to Argentina and Chile, but excluding the Caribbean. The 416 genera make up one third of all 1,250 reptile genera worldwide. Most of these names are still based on Greek and Latin terms (316 and 79, respectively), and about 20 names each are based on local terms, eponyms, and actual localities. The origin of some names remains mysterious (e.g. *Farancia*, *Ficimia*, *Ninia*), although we do offer speculations about them. More than half of all American reptile genera were coined by just 10 individuals, two of whom are still alive. The vast majority of names were coined in an intense period of discovery from around 1820 to 1880 (when many authors did not explain the origin of their names). However, a significant increase of new genus descriptions has

begun in the 21st century with the advent of molecular taxonomy.

Key words: Sauria, Serpentes, Squamata, Crocodylia, Testudines, North America, Central America, South America, New World

INTRODUCTION

The American supercontinent ranges from the Arctic in Canada to the Antarctic parts of Tierra del Fuego in Argentina and Chile. This huge landmass boasts a huge diversity of life, including 3,793 reptile species (Uetz et al., 2024; Uetz & Stylianou, 2018). Note that we exclude the Caribbean from this definition which hosts another 800 species of reptiles or so (as defined by Uetz, 2000, i.e. we exclude Puerto Rico from the Americas although it is politically associated to the United States).

The 3,793 species are currently organized in 416 genera, a number that represents a full third of the world's 1,250 reptile genera. Although there have been several books and monographs that explained the etymology of many genera (e.g. Beolens et al., 2011; Gotch, 1986, 1995), there is no comprehensive survey of all of them, and certainly no further analysis in space and time.

Thus, we have compiled the etymologies of all these genera, and tried to classify them into their source types, that is, whether they originate from Greek or Latin stems, eponyms, or other sources. The latter would include localities, such as *Amapasaurus*, named after the Brazilian state of Amapa, or mythology, such as *Lachesis*, named after one of the three Fates in Greek mythology. A surprisingly large group of genera was actually named after other genera, such as *Ameivula*, supposedly a diminutive form of *Ameiva*. Finally, we identify several genera whose etymology remains unknown, such as those of *Ficimia* or *Riama*, even though we take the liberty to speculate about the origin of some of them. All etymologies and their classification are summarized in an appendix, and tabulated for easier access in a supplementary table. The etymologies are also available through the Reptile Database (Uetz et al., 2024).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We compiled etymologies from several previously published lists such as that of Ellin Beltz (2006), books such as those on the herpetofauna of Mexico by Lemos-Espinal et al. (2007, 2015), websites such as Wikipedia, etymological dictionaries (e.g. Werner, 1972) and Greek and Latin dictionaries, as well as original descriptions of these species. Unfortunately, many older species descriptions do not explain their origin, even though many can be inferred from their Greek and Latin stems. However, some names remain completely obscure, which is made more complicated by the fact that some authors, e.g. John Edward Gray, are thought to have formed names out of random characters, without any explanation.

Brown's lexicon (1954) has been a classic tool in zoological nomenclature, although it is occasionally insufficient, so we rely on some other sources. For **Greek**, Bailly (1895), Beekes & Van Beek (2010), Borrer (1960), Diggie et al. (2021) and Liddell & Scott (1996); **Latin** is covered by the dictionaries of Borrer (1960), De Vaan (2008) and Glare (2012). Portuguese followed the famous Aurelio, of Ferreira et al., 2010, and VV. AA., 2021, and the native Tupí terms were defined with the help of Barbosa (1951), Dias (1858), Navarro (2008), Carvalho (1987) and Sampaio (1987). Additionally, some names

were identified based on Beolens et al. (2011).

In the interest of space, we do not provide all original references for all genera, but we do list the authors of genera, and the type species in the supplement. More details on these names, including their detailed distribution, can be obtained from the Reptile Database using the general URL

<https://reptile-database.reptarium.cz//species?genus=genus&species=epithet>, e.g. <https://reptile-database.reptarium.cz//species?genus=Abronia&species=deppii> for Deppe's Arboreal Alligator Lizard, *Abronia deppii*, the type species of the genus *Abronia*. The etymology and source reference for each genus is listed in the database entry of the type species that is listed in **Supplementary Table 1**. Note that we do not provide the etymologies of all species, a project that we will address in a forthcoming paper.

RESULTS

Not surprisingly, most genus names are derived from **Greek** and **Latin** stems, namely 316 and 79 names, respectively. In fact, we found 31 genera that combine Greek and Latin terms, e.g. *Calamodontophis*, a combination of the Latin *calamus*, meaning reed or cane, and the Greek terms *odontos* (ὀδόντος), mean-

ing tooth, plus the Greek *ophis*, (ὄφις), a snake. Other genus names are combinations of classic words and other terms, e.g. names of people, so called eponyms.

In fact, **eponyms** are commonly used for genus names and we found 19 eponymous names, ranging from *Alexandresaurus* to *Xantusia*. The former was named after Brazilian naturalist Alexandre Rodrigues Ferreira, while the latter was named after John Xantus, (also known as Louis de Vesey, 1825–1894), a Hungarian-born naturalist who arrived in the US in 1850. Typically, eponyms are coined in combination with a Greek or Latin term, as in *Alexandresaurus*, which contains the Greek word *sauros* (σαῦρος) for lizard. In fact, 39 genera contain the Greek term *sauros*, which is thus almost as common as the Greek *ophis* (ὄφις), a snake, which is used in 46 genus names, ranging from *Amnesteophis* to *Ungaliophis*.

A surprising 22 genus names are based on **local words** or **languages**, such as the snake genus *Mixcoatlus*, which has been named after the Náhuatl word *Mixcoatl*, meaning 'cloud serpent,' a god of the Aztecs and other Mesoamerican civilizations. We also included Spanish and Portuguese words in the "local" category, given that these are based on local words, even if the source languages were introduced by colonial powers. An example is the lizard genus name *Varzea*, a feminine noun from the

Portuguese várzea, actually a pre-Roman word of Iberian origin, meaning “flooded river bank,” in allusion to the apparent preferred habitat of these species.

Many genus names are based on **locality** information which often provides useful information about the origin of a genus. We have already mentioned *Amapasaurus* above, but other examples are *Brasiliscincus* or less obvious cases such as *Paikwaophis*, named after the river name “Paikwa”, referring to its type locality in Guyana.

Finally, a smaller number of names comes from **mythology**. We already mentioned *Lachesis* above. Another example is *Iphisa*, a lizard genus named after an individual in the *Metamorphoses*, the most famous book of Roman poet Ovid (ca. 43 BC – AD 17).

We were unable to elucidate seven names, and thus categorized them as **unknown**, including *Anniella*, *Emoia*, *Farancia*, *Ficimia*, *Holcosus*, *Ninia* and *Riama*, although we speculate about the origin of some. Five of these names were coined by John Edward Gray, who is known to have used random but euphonious words as genus names, hence we can only speculate about the origin of some of them. One, *Emoia*, may be named after “*Emo*”, a name that Gray 1845 used for this species without further explanation.

Table 1. A classification of American genus etymologies. Some genera are based on combinations, such as a place name and a Greek terms (e.g. ophis, for snake), hence the numbers do not add up to the 416 American genera. See text for further details.

Class	number of genera
Greek	316
Latin	79
Local names	22
Eponym	19
Locality	18
Genus	17
Unknown	9
Mythology	7
Random	2

Overall, a few individuals coined a large number of genus names. Earlier authors, obviously, had an advantage, but novel technologies such as DNA sequencing have allowed more recent authors to create many new genus names as well. For example, the most prolific author in terms of new genera was Edward Drinker Cope (1840-1897), an American zoologist who described 37 new (American) genera that are still in use today. The only contemporary herpetologists in the list are Blair Hedges, who described 15 new American genera, most of them with his co-authors Caitlin E. Conn and Molly Schools, and Miguel T. Rodrigues, who described 10 new genera. Together, the top 11 authors described 225 out of 416 genera or a whopping 54%.

Table 2. Top 11 most prolific authors describing new genera. Living authors are highlighted in bold. For biographic details we refer the reader to Adler (1989; 2007; 2012).

Name	Genera
Edward Drinker Cope (1840-1897)	37
Leopold Josef Fitzinger (1802-1884)	35
John Edward Gray (1800-1875)	33
Johann Georg Wagler (1800-1832)	30
André Marie Constant Dumeril (1774-1860) & Gabriel Bibron (1806-1848)	17
Spencer Fullerton Baird (1823-1887) & Albert Girard (1860-1914)	17 (11)*
S. Blair Hedges (1957-)	15
Wilhelm Peters (1815-1883)	13
Arend Friedrich August Wiegmann (1802-1841)	12
Miguel T. Rodrigues (1953-)	10
George Albert Boulenger (1858-1937)	9
Total	225

*Baird authored 17 genera, 11 as co-author with Girard.

Figure 1. American reptile genera described per decade. By far the most genera were described in the discovery period from ca. 1820 through 1890, with a recent rebound starting in the 1990s, probably driven by molecular techniques. The 2020s would currently extrapolate to about 24 new genera, based on numbers in mid 2024.

DISCUSSION

An intense discussion has started recently about the use of eponyms which are widely considered as colonial, patriarchal, sexist, and thus racist, given that they are often dedicated to older white men who were frequently active during colonial rule (e.g. Guedes et al., 2023, Slabin, 2023). While there is certainly some truth to that, the problem has been recognized and there is a strong trend to counter it. Interestingly, among the 22 “local” genus names in our list, 13 (59%) have been coined in the 18th and 19th century, with a long gap of more than 100 years after that. The first “modern” local name, *Boiruna* Zaher 1996 was coined after the Tupi-Guarani word “Mboi+r+ú” [= which eats snakes] +una [= black], in allusion to the ophiophagous habits of these black snakes. However, since 2009, another eight local names have been coined for new genera, and we expect this trend to continue. Whether this will affect the use of eponyms is another question, but we clearly see a trend to apply eponyms more to local heroes, such as the latest name in our list, *Galvarinus*, which is derived from “Galvarino,” a famous Mapuche warrior who fought the invasion and attempted servitude of the Mapuche people by the colonial Spaniards in Chile during the sixteenth century.

After finishing the list of American genera, we will continue to work on the genus etymologies of the remaining 835 genera and finally all reptile species. It will be interesting to see if the patterns we elucidated in this study will apply to species names as well, but we are confident that the use of Greek and Latin will continue to decrease, given a more international community of herpetologists who will be less trained in classical European languages but put more emphasis on local cultural and conservation issues.

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SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE

Table S1. List of all genera, together with their higher taxa, genus authors and year, etymology, classification and the actual etymology.

APPENDIX: etymologies of all American reptile genera

As noted in a previous contribution (Lavilla et al., 2022), we tried to compile the source or stem of each genus name, and its language of origin (**A.** Arawak. **C.** Caribe. **D.** Dutch. **E.** English **G.** Greek. **Gu.** Guaraní. **I.** Italian **L.** Latin. **M.** Mapudungun. **N.** Náhuatl. **OE.** Old English. **P.** Portuguese. **Pa.** Patamona. **Q.** Quechua. **S.** Spanish. **SL.** Several languages. **T.** Tupi. **Ta.** Taíno. **Y.** Yanomamö). We have added a quote from the original description to provide context and the original explanation, in case the etymology was not explicit. **Question marks [?]** before a name indicate that the original language remains unclear; a question mark at the end of an etymology reflects that we have no further information about the origin or meaning of the name in the original description. Readers who have corrections or additions are requested to send them to the authors who will post them as updates in the Reptile Database. Note that etymologies of genera can be found there in the entry of the type species.

Abronia: G. *abros* (ἀβρός), delicate, graceful, beauteous, pretty + L. *-ia*, or G. *-ia*, sux denoting pertaining to. [? perhaps in reference to the delicate nature of the tail (Lemos-Espinal & Dixon 2013)]. Note that there is also a plant genus *Abronia*. *Abronia* Gray, 1838. Sauria: Anguillidae.

Acanthochelys: G. *akanthos* (ἀκανθός), thorn + G. *chelys* (χέλυς), tortoise. [“...back of neck covered with conical spines...”]. *Acanthochelys* Gray, 1873. Testudines: Chelidae.

Acratosaura: G. *akratos* (ἄκρατος), unmixed, sheer + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [“...From the Greek *akratos*, meaning “unmixed, pure”; here intended to reflect its unmixed condition after being dismembered from the polyphyletic *Colobosaura*...”]. *Acratosaura* Rodrigues, Pellegrino, Dixo, Verdade, Pavan, Argolo & Sites, 2007. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Actinemys: G. *actinos* (ἄκτινός), rays + G. *emys* (ἐμύς), fresh-water tortoise [“...Young, with radiating striae upon the scales, the center of which remains for a long time granular, as in *Testudo tabulata*...”]. *Actinemys* Agassiz, 1857. Testudines: Emydidae.

Adelphicos: G. *adelphicos* (ἀδελφικός), brotherly. [Se per l’abito generale questo serpente non può essere allontanato dal gen. *Rabdosoma*...]. *Adelphicos* Jan, 1862. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Adelphostigma: G. *adelphos* (ἀδελφός), brother + G. *stigma* (στίγμα), mark, spot. [“...From the composition of the Ancient Greek words ἀδελφός (*adelphos* [twin, brother]) and στίγμα (*stigma* [mark, brand, spot]) (Liddell and Scott, 1883; Brown, 1954), in reference to the paired dorsal spots typical of the species here included in this new genus. The genus name is feminine...”]. *Adelphostigma* Abegg, Santos-Jr, Costa, Battilana, Graboski, Vianna, Azevedo, Fagundes, Castille, Prado, Bonatto, Zaher & Grazziotin, 2022. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Adercosaurus: G. *aderces* (ἀδερχής), unseen, invisible + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [“...From the Greek *aderkes* (something unexpected or unseen) + *sauros*—an unexpected lizard. Gender masculine...”]. *Adercosaurus* Myers & Donnelly, 2001. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Advenus: L. *advenus*, foreign, alien; migrant; recently arrived. [“...The generic name *Advenus* is a masculine noun derived from the Latin *ad-*

vena (“stranger”), referring to the distribution of this species in Middle America when all of its close relatives are on Caribbean islands...”]. *Advenus* Schools & Hedges, 2021. Sauria: Diploglossidae.

Agkistrodon: G. *agkistron* (ἄγκιστρον), a fish-hook + G. *odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [“...The extremity of the upper jaw furnished with two hollow fangs or canine teeth...”]. *Agkistrodon* Palisot de Beauvois 1799. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Alexandresaurus: P. Alexandre, a given name + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. Honoring Alexandre Rodrigues Ferreira (1756-1815), Brazilian naturalist. *Alexandresaurus* Rodrigues, Pellegrino, Dixo, Verdade, Pavan, Argolo & Sites, 2007. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Alligator: S. *El lagarto*, the lizard. [“...Les colons et voyageurs anglois emploient le mot *alligator* dans les mêmes circonstances où ceux des autres nations font usage de celui de caïman, comme pour désigner un crocodile plus commun ou plus petit, etc., sans aucun caractère fixe. Quoiqu’il ait une tournure latine, il n’a point de rapport avec son étimologie apparente. Si l’on en croyoit quelques-uns de leurs auteurs, il viendrait de *legateer* ou *allegater*,

qui seroit le nom du crocodile dans quelques endroits de l’Inde; mais je n’en trouve nulle indication authentique: je pense bien plutôt que c’est une corruption du portugais *lagarto*, qui vient lui-même de *lacerta*; car Hawkins écrivoit *alagartos*, et Sloane, *allagator*. Dans la prononciation angloise, il n’y a presque pas de différence entre *allagator* et *allegater*, ou même *allegater*...”]. *Alligator* Cuvier, 1807. Crocodylia: Alligatoridae.

Alopoglossus: G. *alopos* (ἄλοπος), not scutched + G. *glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue. [“...Tongue moderately elongate, arrow-headed, without imbricate scale-like papilla, these being replaced by oblique plicae converging towards the median line...”]. *Alopoglossus* Boulenger, 1885. Sauria: Alopoglossidae.

Amapasaurus: P. Amapá, a Brazilian state + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [“...O nome *Amapasaurus* deriva de Amapá, Território Federal, a região de onde procedem os exemplares estudados...”]. *Amapasaurus* Cunha, 1970. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Amastridium: Uncertain. (1) G. *mas-tr-* (μάστρ-), seeker, searcher, one who looks for + G. *-idium* (-ιδιον), diminutive suffix. According to Wilson (1988), “The first letter of the

name was most likely intended by Cope to represent a euphonic alpha, affecting the pronunciation but not the meaning. Given such was the case, the meaning would be “a little searcher,” in apparent reference to the snake’s size and foraging habits. It is possible, however, that Cope used the a- as an intensive alpha, meaning “very much,” thus signifying “very much the little searcher.” (2) G. *Amastris* (Ἀμαστρίς), daughter of Otanes, wife of Xerxes, and mother of Artaxerxes I. (3) G. *Amastris* (Ἀμαστρίς), city in Paphlagonia on the southern coast of the Euxine Pontus, called Cronna by Homer. *Amastridium* Cope, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Amblyrhynchus: G. *amblys* (ἀμβλύς), blunt, dulled, with the edge taken off + G. *rhygchos* (ρύγχος), snout, beak. [“...Caput breve, truncatum, supra tuberculatum...”]. *Amblyrhynchus* Bell, 1825. Sauria: Iguanidae.

Ameiva: T. *ameiva*, vernacular name for some lizards, probably from the Tupí words *ambere*, lizard + *aíba*, not fit for eating. [?]. *Ameiva* Meyer 1795. Sauria: Teiidae.

Ameivula: L. *Ameiva*, lizard genus due to Meyer, 1795 + L. *-ula*, diminutive suffix. [“...The new name *Ameivula* is a feminine noun in the

nominative singular and a diminutive form of *Ameiva*...”]. *Ameivula* Harvey, Ugueto & Gutberlet, 2012. Sauria: Teiidae.

Amerotyphlops: L. *americanus*, from America + G. *typhlos* (τυφλός), blind. [“...The generic name is a masculine noun formed from the adjective *americanus* (*a, um*; ‘from America’) and Greek noun *typhlops* (the blind)...”]. *Amerotyphlops* Hedges, Marion, Lipp, Marin & Vidal, 2014. Serpentes: Typhlopidae.

Amnesteophis: G. *amnestos* (ἀμνηστος), unremembered, forgotten + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...*Amnesteophis* (forgotten snake), from Greek *amnēstos* (ἀμνηστος, “forgotten, no longer remembered”) + connective *-e-* + *ophis* (ὄφις, “snake”)...”]. *Amnesteophis* Myers, 2011. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Amnisiophis: L. *amnis*, river (real/personified), stream; current; (running) water + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...From the combination of the Latin word *amnis* (stream of water, river) and the Greek word *οφίς* (*ophis* [snake])...”] (Liddell and Scott, 1883; Brown, 1954). This name was chosen in reference to the habit of the monotypic species *A. amoenus*, whose

individuals inhabit the margins of forest streams. The genus name is masculine...”. *Amnisiophis* Abegg, Santos-Jr, Costa, Battilana, Graboski, Vianna, Azevedo, Fagundes, Castille, Prado, Bonatto, Zaher & Grazziotin, 2022. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Amphisbaena*:** G. *amphisbaina* (ἀμφίσβαινα), from G. *amphis* (ἀμφίς), both ways, double + G. *bainein* (βαίνειν), to go, to walk; vernacular name of a reptile able to move forwards and backwards. [?]. *Amphisbaena* Linnaeus 1758. Sauria: Amphisbaenidae.

***Anadia*:** G. *anadema* (ἀνάδημα), hairnet, headband. [“...Head with regular many sided shields...”]. *Anadia* Gray, 1845. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Andinosaura*:** S. *Andino*, demonym of the inhabitant of the Andes + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [“...*Andinosaura* (gender feminine), formed from the Spanish *Andino* (from the Andes) and the Latin Sauria (lizard), in reference to its distribution. The suffix is used commonly for gymnophthalmid genera...”]. *Andinosaura* Sánchez-Pacheco, Torres-Carvajal, Aguirre-Peña-fiel, Nunes, Verrastro, Rivas, Rodrigues, Grant & Murphy, 2018. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Anelytropsis*:** G. *anelytos* (ανήλυτος), unresolved + G. *ops* (ὄψ, ὄψ), face, eye. [“...The present form is essentially interesting as introducing for the first time to the Western continent, the family of the Anelytropidae, or the Typhlopthalm lizards with the eye entirely concealed...”]. *Anelytropsis* Cope, 1885. Sauria: Dibamidae.

***Anilius*:** G. *anilees* (ἀνηλεής), without pity, unmerciful. [“...Sei giftig...”]. *Anilius* Oken, 1816. Serpentes: Aniliidae.

***Anniella*:** Unclear. Probably from L. *annellus*, little ring, or from G. *aneleos* (ἀνέλεος), unmerciful [?]. *Anniella* Gray, 1852. Sauria: Anguillidae.

***Anolis*:** C. *anolis*, a vernacular name of probable Caribbean origin, first cited in literature by Du Tertre (1754: 352) for Guadeloupe Island. *Anolis* Daudin, 1802. Sauria: Anolidae.

***Anomalepis*:** G. *anomalos* (ἀνώμαλος), uneven, irregular; which deviate from a general rule, anomalous + G. *lepis* (λεπίς), a scale. [“...Chez les autres Typhlopiens, au contraire, les plaques de la tête ont une disposition tout à fait spéciale, qui ne se rencontre que dans cette famille..”] *Anomalepis*

Jan, 1860. Serpentes: Anomalepididae.

Anotosaura: G. *an-* (αν-), prefix meaning without or lacking + G. *otos* (ὄτος), ear + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [...Genero de Teiideo desprovido de ouvido aparente...]. *Anotosaura* Amaral, 1933. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Apalone: G. *apalon* (ἀπαλόν), soft to the touch, tender + G. *chelones* (χελώνης), tortoise. [...The name is contracted from *apalochelone* meaning Soft turtle...]. *Apalone* Rafinesque, 1832. Testudines: Trionychidae.

Apographon: G. *apographo* (ἀπογράφω), to write off, copy. [...From the Greek “*Apographos*” (masculine noun, translated as “copy” or “transcript”), in reference to its resemblance with the genus *Tomodon*, where it was previously allocated...]. *Apographon* Trevine, Grazziotin, Giraudo, Sallesbery-Pinchera, Vianna & Zaher, 2022. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Apostolepis: G. *apostos* (ἀπωστός), thrust or driven away from + G. *lepis* (λεπίς), a scale. [...*Apostolepis*, in which the prefrontals are obliterated...]. *Apostolepis* Cope, 1862. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Arcanumophis: L. *arcantum*, secret, private, hidden + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [...From Latin *arcantum*, meaning mystery and Greek *ophis*, meaning serpent...]. *Arcanumophis* Smaga, Ttito & Catenazzi, 2019. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Aristelliger: G. *ari-* (ἀρι-), good, excellent + L. *stella* (star), in apparent reference to the prominent pale centers of the scapular ocelli which are typical components of the color pattern of members of this genus, including the type species, *A. lar* (fide Bauer & Russell 1993). *Aristelliger* Cope, 1861. Sauria: Sphaerodactylidae.

Arizona: E. Arizona, US American territory (state since 1912). Probably from the Native American Tohono O’odham (Pima) *ali şonak*, small spring or place of the small spring. [?]. *Arizona* Kenicott in Baird, 1859. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Arthrosaura: G. *arthron* (ἄρθρον), limb; joint + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [...Limbs well developed, pentadactyle...]. *Arthrosaura* Boulenger, 1885. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Aspidoscelis: G. *aspidion* (ασπίδιον), small shield + G. *skelos* (σκέλος), leg

[?]. This likely refers to the enlarged scales that are apparent on the hind limbs. *Aspidoscelis* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Teiidae.

Aspronema: G. *aspro* (ἄσπρο), white + G. *nema* (νήμα), that which is spun, thread, yarn. [...The generic name (*Aspronema*) is a neuter noun derived from the Greek adjective *aspro* (white) and noun *nema* (thread), referring to the distinctive narrow and white dorsolateral and ventrolateral stripes present in species of this genus...]. *Aspronema* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Atractus: G. *atraktos* (ἄτρακτος), spindle, arrow. [...Caput pro trunci volumine nimis parvum, minutum, indistinctum, longulum, aequae fere altum ac latum, rostro longulo subtruncatum...]. *Atractus* Wagler, 1828. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Atropoides: G. *Atropos* (Ἄτροπος), the eldest of the three Fates + G. *-eides* (-ειδής), suffix indicating resemblance. [...The genus name is derived from the Greek words “*atropos*,” one of the three fates in Greek mythology who cut the thread of life, and *oides*, meaning “similar to, or having the nature of. (The first Fate is Clotho who spins the thread of life, after which it is

measured by Lachesis, the second Fate)...]. Names ending in *-eides* are substantiated adjectives and are masculine according to Article 30.1.4.4 of the Code. *Atropoides* Werman, 1992. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Aurivela: L. *auris*, the ear + L. *velare*, to cover (body or part of body), clothe. [...The genus *Aurivela* is a feminine Latin noun in the nominative singular derived from the Latin words *auris* meaning ear and *velatus* meaning covered or concealed. The new name alludes to the auricular flap diagnostic of this genus...]. *Aurivela* Harvey, Ugueto & Gutberlet, 2012. Sauria: Teiidae.

Bachia: G. *baktra* (βάκτρα), wand, stick, cudgel (*vide* Tim Williams, *in litt.*). [?]. *Bachia* Gray, 1845. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Baliodyras: G. *balios* (βαλιός), spotted, dappled + G. *dryas* (δρυάς), (ref. to a nymph) inhabitant of trees. [...*Baliodyras* is a masculine noun from the Greek βαλιός, spotted, dappled, and δρυάς, a kind of snake...]. *Baliodyras* Zaher & Prudente, 2019. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Barisia: Unclear. Probably from G. *barys* (βαρύς), heavy + G. *-ia* (-ία), suffix commonly used to indicate

belonging, origin, or quality. [?]. Apparently in reference to the robust body of *B. imbricata*, according to Lemos-Espinal & Dixon 2013. *Barisia* Gray, 1838. Sauria: Anguillidae.

Basiliscus: *G. basiliscos* (βασιλίσκος), princelet, chieftain (here, in the sense of a crowned creature). [In Laurenti (1768), “...Occiput intra cava membranacea squamulis tecta, præalta, conica, compressa...”. In Wagler (1830) description: “...occiput lobatum...”]. *Basiliscus* Wagler, 1830. Sauria: Corytophanidae.

Bipes: *L. bi-*, two, twice; double; having two + *L. pes*, foot. [“...Point de pattes postérieures; les antérieures très-petites...”]. *Bipes* Latreille, 1801. Sauria: Bipedidae.

Boa: *L. boa*, a large snake that, according to Pliny, was found in the Vatican hills, near Rome; owes its name to the fact that, early in their lives, they feed on milk from cows (*bos*). [?]. *Boa* Linnaeus 1758. Serpentes: Boidae.

Bogertophis: Bogert + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. Honouring Charles Mitchill Bogert (1908-1992), US American herpetologist.

Bogertophis Dowling & Price, 1988. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Boiruna: *T. mboîa*, snake + *T. û*, to eat + *T. una*, dark, black; also, *T. mboi-una*, vernacular name for the black snake also known as *muçurana*. [“...from the Tupi-Guarani ‘Mboi + r + á (= which eats snakes) + una (black), in allusion to the ophiophagous habits of these black snakes...”]. *Boiruna* Zaher, 1996. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Bothriechis: *G. bothros* (βόθρος), any pit or hole + *echi[dna]*. (ἔχιδνα), an adder, viper. [“...Eine Gattung, die zwischen *Bothrops* und *Atropos* steht, mit jener durch das grosse Supraorbitalschild, mit dieser durch die Grösse, Lage und Begrenzung der Thränengruben, durch den Mangel der Kiele an den Schuppen des Vorderkopfes übereinstimmt...”]. *Bothriechis* Peters, 1859. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Bothrocophias: *G. bothros* (βόθρος), any pit or hole + *G. cophias* (κωφίας), the deaf adder. [“...The generic name is derived from the Greek words *bothros*, meaning pit, and *kophias*, meaning snake or adder; the gender of this name is masculine...”]. *Bothrocophias* Gutberlet & Campbell, 2001. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Bothrops: G. *bothros* (βόθρος), any pit or hole. [...fovea utrinque inter nares et oculos intermedia...]. *Bothrops* Wagler, 1824. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Brasiliscincus: SL Brasil, a South-American country + L. *scincus*, a kind of lizard. [...The generic name (*Brasiliscincus*) is a masculine noun derived from the Latin *scincus* (skink) and refers to the distribution of this genus of skinks, centered in Brazil (Portuguese: Brasil)...]. *Brasiliscincus* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Caaeteboia: T. *kaã-etê*, forest; virgin forest + T. *mboia*, snake. [...The genus was named after the Brazilian indigenous Tupi word *Caa-etê* (= “true forest”) + *Boia* (derived from the Tupi *Mboi*, “snake”), gender feminine...]. *Caaeteboia* Zaher, Grazziotin, Cadle, Murphy, Moura-Leite & Bonatto, 2009. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Cachryx: G. *cachryx* (κάχρυς), parched barley. [...Tail short, at, covered with verticils of strong, erect, conic spinous scales...]. *Cachryx* Cope, 1866. Sauria: Iguanidae.

Caiman: Ta. *caiman*, vernacular name. [?]. *Caiman* Spix, 1825. Crocodylia: Alligatoridae.

Calamodontophis: L. *calamus*, reed, cane + G. *odonto-* (ὀδόντο-), tooth + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Calamodontophis* Amaral, 1963. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Callisaurus: G. *calli* (καλλι), beautiful + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [...nous avons été forcés d’en former un petit genre distinct auquel nous avons donné le nom de *callisaurus* pour indiquer la gentillesse de ce petit animal...]. *Callisaurus* Blainville, 1835. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

Callopistes: G. *callopistes* (καλλωπιστής), one who adorns himself, dandy. [...Der Gattungname ist nach dem griechischen καλλωπίζειν, ausschmücken, gebildet, wegen der schönen Zeichnung der einzigen mir bekannten Art; im deutschen Schmuck eidechse...]. *Callopistes* Gravenhorst, 1838. Sauria: Teiidae.

Calyptommatus: G. *calypto* (καλύπτω), to cover with; hidden, concealed + G. *ommatos* (ὄμματος), eye. [...Como estes pequenos lagartos além de mostrarem redução acentuada nos apêndices têm o olho totalmente coberto por uma escama ocular, o mais elevado nível de adaptação à fossorialidade encontrado em Teiidae, reservo-lhes o nome de *Calyptommatus*, do grego

calypto = oculto, escondido; *omatus* = olho...”. *Calyptommatius* Rodrigues, 1991. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Caparaonia: P. Caparaó, mountain range in SE Brazil + L. *-ia*, suffix denoting belonging to. [“...Named for the Caparaó mountains, the type locality, and meaning ‘from Caparaó.’...”]. *Caparaonia* Rodrigues, Cassimiro, Pavan, Curcio, Verdade & Machado Pellegrino, 2009. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Caretta: C. *caret*, vernacular name for these turtles, according to Rochefort (1658; 1665). [?]. *Caretta* Rafinesque, 1814. Testudines: Cheloniidae.

Carphophis: G. *carpho* (κάρφος), a dry stalk or any small dry body + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...Κάρφη, fétu; ὄφις, serpent...”]. *Carphophis* Gervais in d’Orbigny, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Cemophora: G. *ceso* (κημός), a muzzle; nose bag for horses + G. *phoros* (φορός), bearing. [“...Rostril (sic) very prominent, obtusely trihedral, produced slightly between the prefontals...”]. *Cemophora* Cope, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Cenaspis: L. *cena*, dinner/supper; principal Roman meal (evening) + G. *aspis* (ἄσπίς), *asp*, venomous snake. [“...The generic name is derived from the Latin *cena*, meaning dinner, and *aspis*, meaning a kind of snake, in reference to predation on the single known individual of this snake. The name taken literally means ‘dinner snake.’...”]. *Cenaspis* Campbell, Smith & Hall, 2018. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Centrosaura: L. *centrum*, center + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [“...*Centrosaura* (gender feminine) is derived from the Latin *centrum* (center or middle) and the Greek *σαύρα*, *saura* (lizard), in reference to its geographic distribution in Central America...”]. *Centrosaura* Vásquez-Restrepo, Ibáñez, Sánchez-Pacheco & Daza, 2019. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Cercophis: G. *cercos* (κέρκος) tail + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Cercophis* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Cercosaura: G. *cercos* (κέρκος) tail + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [“...*Κέρκος*, cauda, et *σαύρα* lacerta...”] *Cercosaura* Wagler, 1830. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Cerrophidion: S. *cerro*, an isolated elevation of land, of lesser height

than a mountain + *G. ophidion* (ὄφιδιον), a kind of snake. [...The genus name comes from the Spanish *cerro*, meaning mountain, an allusion to the habitat, and the Greek *ophidion*, meaning small snake..."]. *Cerrophidion* Campbell & Lamar, 1992. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Chapinophis: *S. Chapín*, demonym of the natives of Guatemala + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [...The genus name is derived from the Guatemalan colloquialism *Chapín*, referring to a Guatemalan or something from Guatemala, and the Greek *ophis*, meaning a serpent. The generic name is masculine..."]. *Chapinophis* Campbell & Smith, 1998. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Charina: *G. charis* (χάρις), loveliness, grace + L. *-ina*, feminine suffix sometimes with diminutive implications. [?]. *Charina* Gray, 1849. Serpentes: Boidae.

Chatogekko: *S. / P. chato*, flat + Malay *gekoq*, vernacular name of a lizard. [...A composite word from the Spanish and Portuguese ‘Chato’, derived from the G. ‘*Platus*’, meaning ‘flat’ and referring to its pug-nosed snout; and *gekko* from the Malay ‘*gekoq*’, onomatopoeic of the call of the species *Gekko gecko* and the common name to all limbed gekkotans..."]. *Chatogekko* Gam-

ble, Daza, Colli, Vitt & Bauer, 2011. Sauria: Sphaerodactylidae.

Chelonia: *G. chelones* (χελώνης), tortoise. *Chelônê* (Χελώνη) was a nymph who was turned into a turtle as punishment for not attending the wedding of Zeus and Hera. [?]. *Chelonia* Brongniart, 1800. Testudines: Cheloniidae.

Chelonoidis: *G. chelones* (χελώνης), tortoise + G. *-oides* (-οειδής), suffix indicating likeness. [?]. *Chelonoidis* Fitzinger, 1835. Testudines: Testudinidae.

Chelus: *G. chelys* or *chelus* (χέλυσ), tortoise. [?]. *Chelus* Duméril, 1806. Testudines: Chelidae.

Chelydra: *G. chelydros* (χέλυδρος), an amphibious serpent, a kind of tortoise. [?]. *Chelydra* Schweigger, 1812. Testudines: Chelydridae.

Chersodromus: *G. chersos* (χέρσος), dry land, land + *G. dromos* (δρόμος), a course, running, race. [...Af χέρρος eller χέρσος, öde udyrket Land, ogδρομέω, löber..."]. *Chersodromus* Reinhardt, 1861. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Chironius: *G. chiros* (ξηρός), dry land + L. *-ius*, quality or nature of. [?]. *Chironius* Fitzinger, 1826. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Chlorosoma: *G. chloros* (χλωρός), greenish-yellow, pale green + *G. soma* (σῶμα), body. [“...Χλωρός viridis et σῶμα...”]. *Chlorosoma* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Chrysemys: *G. chrysos* (χρυσός), gold + *G. emys* (ἐμύς), freshwater tortoise. [?]. *Chrysemys* Gray, 1844. Testudines: Emydidae.

Claudius: *L. claudo*, to shut something that is open, to close, shut up. [“...Carapace completely ossified, extending much beyond plastron anteriorly and posteriorly...”]. *Claudius* Cope, 1865. Testudines: Kinosternidae.

Clelia: *L. Cloelia*, one of the hostages given to the Etruscan king Lars Porsena during a war with Rome. She escaped captivity and swam across the Tiber River to freedom, an act of bravery that made her a symbol of courage and virtue. [?]. *Clelia* Fitzinger, 1826. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Clemmys: *G. clemmys* (κλεμμύς), tortoise. [“...Als Benennung dieser Gattung habe ich Clemmys, Diebkrotte, gewählt...”]. *Clemmys* Ritgen, 1828. Testudines: Emydidae.

Clonophis: *G. clonos* (κλώνός), branch or sprig (of a tree) + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Clonophis* Cope, 1889. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Cnemidophorus: *G. cnemidophoros* (κνημιδοφόρος), wearing greaves. [“...κνημιδοφόρος, ocreis armatus...”]. *Cnemidophorus* Wagler, 1830. Sauria: Teiidae.

Coleodactylus: *G. coleos* (κολεός), sheath + *G. dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [“...claw obliquely retractile into an oval asymmetrical sheath composed of five scales...”]. *Coleodactylus* Parker, 1926. Sauria: Sphaerodactylidae.

Coleonyx: *G. coleos* (κολεός), sheath + *G. onyx* (όνυξ), nail, claw. [“...the end of each toe furnished with large, oblong, convex scales on each side, forming a complete sheath to the small claws, an elongate tapering scale covering the suture between these two scales above...”]. *Coleonyx* Gray, 1845. Sauria: Eublepharidae.

Colobodactylus: Combination of *L. Colobosaura*, lizard genus due to Boulenger, 1877 + *L. Heterodactylus*, lizard genus due to Spix, 1825. [“...Genero de Teideo, perfectamente intermediario a *Heterodactylus* Spix, 1825 e *Colobosaura*

Boulenger, 1887...”]. *Colobodactylus* Amaral, 1933. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Colobosaura: G. *colobos* (κολοβός), docked, curtailed + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [“...In the characterization of *Perodactylus*, “...Limbs short, with well developed digits; the inner finger rudimentary, tubercular, clawless...”]. *Colobosaura* Boulenger, 1887. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Colobosauroides: L. *Colobosaura*, lizard genus due to Boulenger, 1887 + L. *oides*, resembling, having the form of. [“...O novo gênero apresenta certa afinidade com *Anotosaura* Amaral, 1932, *Colobodactylus* Amaral, 1932 e *Colobosaura* Boulenger, 1887...”]. *Colobosauroides* Cunha, Lima-Verde & Lima, 1991. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Coluber: L. *coluber*, serpent, snake. [?]. *Coluber* Linnaeus 1758. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Coniophanes: G. *conios* (κόνιος), dusty + G. *phaino* (φαίνω), appearance. [“...A peculiarity in the coloration of the species consists in the numerous punctulations of the upper and under surface, whence probably the name (κόνιος *pulverulentus*)...”]. *Coniophanes* Hallow-

ell in Cope, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Conolophus: G. *conos* (κώνος), cone; pine-cone + G. *lophos* (λόφος), neck, crest of hill, ridge, crest of a helmet. [?]. *Conolophus* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Iguanidae.

Conophis: G. *conos* (κώνος), cone; pine-cone + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...κώνος, ὄφις...”]. *Conophis* Peters, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Conopsis: G. *conos* (κώνος), cone; pine-cone + G. *opsis* (ὄψις), aspect, appearance. [“...rostral shield protruding, pyramidal, slightly bent upwards...”]. *Conopsis* Günther, 1858. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Contia: [Le] Conte + L. *-ia*, dedicative suffix. Honouring John Lawrence LeConte (1825-1883), US American entomologist and naturalist. *Contia* Baird & Girard, 1852. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Contomastix: G. *contos* (κοντός), short + G. *mastix* (μάστιξ), a whip, scourge. [“...*Contomastix* is a feminine noun in the nominative singular derived from the Greek adjective *kontos*, meaning short, and noun *mastix*, meaning whip. The name alludes to the relatively short tails

of *Contomastix* compared to other whiptail lizards...”]. *Contomastix* Harvey, Ugueto & Gutberlet, 2012. Sauria: Teiidae.

Copeoglossum: G. *copeus* (κοπεύς), a chisel + G. *glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue. [“...The generic name (*Copeoglossum*) is a neuter noun, derived from the Greek nouns *kopeus* (chisel) and *glossa* (tongue), in allusion to the shape of the tongue...”]. *Copeoglossum* Tschudi, 1845. Sauria: Scincidae.

Cophosaurus: G. *cophos* (κωφός), unable to hear, deaf + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [“...aures externae nullae...”]. *Cophosaurus* Troschel, 1852. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

Corallus: G. *corallos* (κόραλλος), coral. [“...c’est donc pour faire allusion traître et méchant de ces reptiles dangereux que j’ai donné à ce genre nouveau le nom de coralle, qui appartenait anciennement à des peuples sauvages et barbares, dont Ovide décrit les cruautés dans ses Œuvres...”]. *Corallus* Daudin, 1803. Serpentes: Boidae.

Coronelaps: L. *corona*, crown; garland, wreath; halo/ring + G. *elaps* (ἔλαψ), a snake. [“...Yellow collar on the parietals...”]. *Coronelaps* Lema & Hofstadler-Deiques, 2010. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Corytophanes: G. *corythos* (κόρυθος), crested + G. *phaneros* (φανερός), visible, manifest. [?]. *Corytophanes* Boie, 1827. Sauria: Corytophanidae.

Crisantophis: S. Crisanta, a given name (fem.) + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. Honouring Crisanta Chaves (1900-1981), Nicaragan naturalist. *Crisantophis* Villa, 1971. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Crocodylurus: G. *crocódilos* (κροκόδιλος), lizard, crocodile + G. *oura* (οὐρᾶ), tail. [“...cauda vero tota rectangula, compressa, supra ad basin planiuscula, carinata, utrinque denticulata...”]. *Crocodylurus* Spix, 1825. Sauria: Teiidae.

Crocodylus: G. *crocódilos* (κροκόδιλος), Greek noun for lizards, later applied to the Nile crocodile. [?]. *Crocodylus* Laurenti 1768. Crocodylia: Crocodylidae.

Crotalus: L. *crotalus*, clapper (used instead of bell), rattle, bell, castanet. [“...Crepitaculum terminale caudae...”]. *Crotalus* Linnaeus 1758. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Crotaphytus: G. *crotaphytis* (κροταφίτης), temporal muscle. [“...Head large, sub-triangular, rounded at the snout and greatly de-

veloped at the temporal region...”]. *Crotaphytus* Holbrook, 1842. Sauria: Crotaphytidae.

Cryophis: G. *cryos* (κρύος), freezing weather, icy cold, frost cold + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“... In allusion to the cool cloud-forest habitat of these snakes in Oaxaca, the genus is herewith given a name derived from the G. *kryos*, cold...”]. *Cryophis* Bogert & Duellman, 1963. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Cryptoblepharus: G. *cryptos* (κρυπτός), hidden, secret + G. *blepharon* (βλέφαρον), eyelid. [“... wegen der nicht völlig fehlenden, nur verborgenen Augenlieder (l.c.) ...”]. *Cryptoblepharus* Wiegmann, 1834. Sauria: Scincidae.

Ctenoblepharys: G. *cthenos* (κτενος), comb + G. *blepharon* (βλέφαρον), eyelid [“...Pholidosis palpebrarum granulata...”]. *Ctenoblepharys* Tschudi, 1845. Sauria: Liolaemidae.

Ctenosaura: G. *ctenos* (κτενός), comb + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [“...crista cornea versus caudam evanescenti denticulatum...”]. *Ctenosaura* Wiegmann, 1828. Sauria: Iguanidae.

Cyclura: G. *cyclos* (κύκλος), ring, circle + G. *oura* (οὐρά), tail [?]. In the

characterization of *Cyclura teres* [“...tail cylindrical, tapering gradually towards the point...”]. *Cyclura* Harlan, 1824. Sauria: Iguanidae.

Cyrtopodion: G. *cyrtos* (κυρτός), bulging, swelling + G. *podion* (πόδιον), foot. [?]. *Cyrtopodion* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Gekkoniidae.

Deirochelys: G. *deire* (δειρή), neck, throat + G. *chelys* (χέλυσ), tortoise. [“...In many respects it recalls the Australian Chelodinae, by the unusual length of its neck...”]. *Deirochelys* Agassiz, 1857. Testudines: Emydidae.

Dendrophidion: G. *dendron* (δένδρον), tree + G. *ophidion* (ὀφίδιον), a kind of snake. [?]. *Dendrophidion* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Dendrosauridion: G. *dendron* (δένδρον), tree + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard + G. *-idion* (-ίδιον), diminutive suffix. [“...The genus name *Dendrosauridion* is derived from the Greek nouns ‘*dendron*’ (tree; neutrum) and ‘*sauridion*’ (small lizard; diminutive, neutrum) and is in allusion to the arboreal habits of the type species...”]. *Dendrosauridion* Lehr, Moravec, Lundberg, Köhler, Catenazzi & Šmíd, 2019. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Dermatemys: G. *dermatos* (δέρματος), skin, hide + G. *emys* (ἐμῦς), freshwater tortoise. [“...scutellis membranaceis tenuissimis defenso...”]. *Dermatemys* Gray, 1847. Testudines: Dermatemydidae.

Dermochelys: G. *derma* (δέρμα) skin, hide + G. *chelys* (χέλυς), turtle. [“...Dans cet ordre je fais un genre distinct de la Tortue à cuir, sous le nom de *Dermochelys*...”]. *Dermochelys* Blainville, 1816. Testudines: Dermochelyidae.

Diadophis: G. *diadema* (διάδημα), a band + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...generally with a light ring on the occipital region...”]. *Diadophis* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Diaphorolepis: G. *diaphoros* (διάφορος), different, unlike + G. *lepis* (λεπίς), a scale. [“...nachdem mir nun ein zweites Exemplar dieser seltenen Art vorliegt, welches kleiner ist und im Wesentlichen nur durch die weit zahlreicheren Subcaudalen sich unterscheidet...”]. *Diaphorolepis* Werner, 1901. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Dibernardia: I. Di Bernardo, a family name + L. -ia, suffix denoting pertaining to. Honouring Marcos

Di Bernardo (1963-2006), Brazilian herpetologist. *Dibernardia* Abegg, Santos Jr., Costa, Battilana, Graboski, Vianna, Azevedo, Fagundes, Castille, Prado, Bonatto, Zaher & Grazziotin, 2022. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Dicrodon: G. *dicros* (δίκρος), forked, split, double + G. *odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [“...De δίκρος, *bifidus*, *furcatus*, doublée, fourchue; et de οδονς, οντος, *dens*, dent...”]. *Dicrodon* Duméril & Bibron, 1839. Sauria: Teiidae.

Diploglossus: G. *diplos* (διπλος), double + G. *glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue. [“...Διπλος, *diplos*, de deux sortes, et de γλωσσα, langue de deux apparences...”]. *Diploglossus* Wiegmann, 1834. Sauria: Diploglossidae.

Diplolaemus: G. *diplos* (διπλος), double + G. *laimos* (λαιμός), throat, gullet. [“...The neck ... has a longitudinal fold on each side ... There is also a distinct transverse fold on the throat...”]. *Diplolaemus* Bell, 1843. Sauria: Leiosauridae.

Dipsas: G. *dipsas* (διψάς), thirsty; causing thirst. [?]. The name is traceable up to Nicander’s *Theriaca* (line 334), describing a venomous serpent, whose bite caused intense

thirst.]. *Dipsas Laurenti* 1768. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Dipsosaurus: G. *dipsos* (δίψος), thirst + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [?]. *Dipsosaurus* Hallowell, 1854. Sauria: Iguanidae.

Ditaxodon: G. *di-* (δι-), two, double + G. *taxis* (τάξις), arrangement, order + G. *odon* (ὀδών), tooth. [“...12 Maxillarzähne, die vorderen klein und allmählich nach hinten zu größer werdend, gefolgt nach einer Lücke von 2 mäßig vergrößerten Furchenzähnen...”]. *Ditaxodon* Hoge, 1958. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Dracaena: L. *dracæna*, or G. (*dracaena*) δράκαινα, a shedragon. [“...*Dragone* ...”]. *Dracaena* Daudin, 1801. Sauria: Teiidae.

Drepanoides: G. *drepanon* (δρέπανον), a scythe; curved sword, scimitar + G. *-oides* (-οειδής), suffix indicating likeness. [“...*nomen novum* for *Drepanodon* Peracca, preoccupied...”]. The genus *Drepanodon* Peracca, 1896 is a junior homonym of *Drepanodon* Nesti, 1826, a Mammal. *Drepanoides* Dunn, 1928. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Dryadosaura: G. *Dryados* (Δρυάδης), tree nymphs, inhabitants of trees + G. *saura* (σαῦρα),

lizard. [“...The genus was named after Greek *Dryades*, meaning ‘woodland nymph’. This was the first name proposed (by Carl Philipp von Martius) for the biogeographical province of the Atlantic Forest...”]. *Dryadosaura* Rodrigues, Freire, Pellegrino & Sites, 2005. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Drymarchon: G. *drymos* (δρυμός), an oak-coppice, forest, wood + G. *archon* (ἄρχων), ruler or leader. [?]. *Drymarchon* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Drymobius: G. *drymos* (δρυμός), an oak-coppice, forest, wood+ G. *bios* (βίος), existence or condition of being alive; life. [?]. *Drymobius* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Drymoluber: L. *Drymobius*, snake genus due to Fitzinger, 1843 + L. *Coluber*, snake genus due to Linnaeus, 1758 . [“...Por seus caracteres dentarios e peníanos, *dichrous* parece próxima e intermediaria aos representantes do genero *Drymobius* e *Coluber*...”]. *Drymoluber* Amaral, 1930. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Dryophylax: G. *drys* (δρῦς), tree + G. *phylax* (φύλαξ), watcher, guard, sentinel. [“...Δρῦς arbor, et φύλαξ

custos...”]. *Dryophylax* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Echinanthera*:** *G. echis* (ἔχις), an adder, viper + *G. antherix* (ἀνθήριξ), the beard of an ear of grain. [?]. In the characterization of the type-species, *Aporophis cyanopleurus* Cope, 1885 [“...this part of the band isolates itself into dark round spots; on the upper edge of the lateral band every other scale has a pale spot in the centre...”]. *Echinanthera* Cope, 1894. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Echinosaura*:** *G. echinos* (ἐχῖνος), the urchin, hedgehog + *G. saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [“...Upper parts granular with enlarged tubercles, the largest of which are spines...”]. *Echinosaura* Boulenger, 1890. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Ecpleopus*:** *G. ecpleos* (ἐκπλεος), complete + *G. pous* (πούς), foot. [“...Ἐκπλέως, au complet; πούς, πόδες, pied...”]. *Ecpleopus* Duméril & Bibron, 1839. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Elapomorphus*:** *G. elaps* (ἔλαψ), a snake, from ἐλαφρός, lightly, buoyantly + *G. morpha* (μορφή), bodily form, build. [?]. *Elapomorphus* Wiegmann in Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Elgaria*:** OE. *elger*, eel-spear (*vide* Lemos-Espinal et al. 2019) + L. -ia, suffix denoting pertaining to. [“...tail much longer than the body, slender...”]. *Elgaria* Gray, 1838. Sauria: Anguidae.

***Emmochliophis*:** *G. emmochlion* (ἐμμόχλιον), ring or socket into which the bolt of a latch is inserted + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...Trunk vertebrae with a large lateral projection in the form of a straight-edged shelf anteriorly emarginate next to the centrum and bearing a lateral rodlike anterior extension fitting into a groove in the posterior portion of the lateral surface of the shelf of the vertebra anterior to it...”]. *Emmochliophis* Fritts & Smith, 1969. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Emoia*:** Unclear; *Emo* as a vernacular name? Probably from Middle-English *emoi*, in turn from L. *emotio*, move away, remove, dislodge. [English names for the included species are The Black Sided Emo, Carteret’s Emo, Baudin’s Emo, and The Emo]. *Emoia* Gray, 1845. Sauria: Scincidae.

***Emydoidea*:** L. *Emys*, chelonian genus due to Duméril 1805 + L. *oides*, suffix indicating resembling, having the form of. [?]. *Emydoidea* Gray, 1870. Testudines: Emydidae.

Enuliophis: G. *en* (έν, from εἷς), one + G. *oule* (οὐλή), a scar + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [...The name *Enuliophis* is from the Greek words *hen* (meaning one), *oule* (scar or mark), and *ophis* (snake). *Enulius* (with the h in *hen* silent and dropped) as originally used by Cope, apparently referred to the single mark (the neck band) characteristic of the type species..."]. *Enuliophis* McCranie & Villa, 1993. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Enulius: G. *en* (έν, from εἷς), one + G. *oule* (οὐλή), a scar (see *Enuliophis*), or G. *en* (έν, from εἷς), one + G. *uli* (ῦλη), the smaller branches of felled timber. [?]. *Enulius* Cope, 1871. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Enyalioides: L. *Enyalius*, lizard genus due to Wagler, 1830 + L. *-oides*, suffix indicating likenes. [?]. *Enyalioides* Boulenger, 1885. Sauria: Hoplocercidae.

Enyalius: G. *enyalius* (ένυάλιος), warrior, warlike, terrible. [...'Ενυάλιος belicosus...']. *Enyalius* Wagler, 1830. Sauria: Leiosauridae.

Epicrates: G. *epicrates* (επικρατές), master of. [...*Epicrates*, is, m. Cic...'] (i.e. name given by Cicero to Pompey in his letters to Atticus, 2,

3). *Epicrates* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Boidae.

Epictia: L. *e-*, without + L. *pictus*, painted (apparently in allusion to the absence of colors) [?]. *Epictia* Gray, 1845. Serpentes: Leptotyphlopidae.

Eretmochelys: G. *eretmon* (έρετμόν), oar + Gr. *chelys* (χέλυς), tortoise. [?]. *Eretmochelys* Fitzinger, 1843. Testudines: Cheloniidae.

Erythrolamprus: G. *erythros* (ερυθρός), red + G. *lampros* (λαμπρός), bright, brilliant, radiant. [...Ερυθρός, ruber et λαμπρός, splendidus...']. *Erythrolamprus* Boie, 1826. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Eunectes: G. *eu-* (εὖ-), well + G. *nectes* (νήκτης) swimmer. [...Wasserschlinger...']. *Eunectes* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Boidae.

Eurolophosaurus: G. *Euros* (Εὖρος), the East wind + G. *lophos* (λόφος), crest of hill, ridge + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [...G. Euro- (eastern), lopho- (ridge), sauros (lizard), referring to the association of this group of species with the Serra da Espinhaço ridge of mountains in eastern Brazil...']. *Eurolophosaurus* Frost, Rodrigues, Grant & Titus, 2001. Sauria: Tropicoduridae.

Euspondylus: G. *eu-* (ἐϋ-), good, well, genuine + G. *spondylion* (σπονδύλιον), neck vertebra. [“... Jugulum collari distincto...”]. *Euspondylus* Tschudi, 1845. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Eutrachelophis: G. *eu-* (εὖ-), well; good, noble + G. *trachelos* (τράχηλος), the neck, throat + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“... The intended meaning of the generic name is “beautiful-necked snake.” It is compounded from the prefix *eu-* (beautiful) + *trachelos* (neck) + *ophis* (a serpent), all from the Greek. Gender masculine...”]. *Eutrachelophis* Myers & Mcdowell, 2014. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Exila: L. *exilis*, strict, narrow, thin, slender, lank, small, meagre, poor [“...The generic name (*Exila*) is a feminine noun derived from the Latin adjective *exilis* (lean), alluding to the thin body shape and unusually low number of midbody scale rows in this species (24–28)...”]. *Exila* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Exiliboa: L. *exilis*, small, thin; poor + L. *Boa*, snake genus due to Linnaeus, 1758. [“...A small, nearly unicolorated, prehensile-tailed boa...”]. *Exiliboa* Bogert, 1968. Serpentes: Boidae.

Farancia: Unknown. Possibly a name that was made up by Gray. None of our sources has a plausible explanation for this name. *Farancia* Gray, 1842. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Ficimia: Unknown. Possibly a name that was made up by Gray. None of our sources has a plausible explanation for this name. *Ficimia* Gray, 1849. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Furcifer: L. *furcifer*, a yoke-bearer, gallows rogue, hang-dog, rascal. [?]. *Furcifer* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Chamaeleonidae.

Galvarinus: S. Galvarino (? - 1557), Mapuche warrior during the Spanish conquest of Chile (in turn from M. *Kallfürüingi*, blue colihue, a cane of the genus *Chusquea*) + L. *-inus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to; connected with. [“...The genus epithet *Galvarinus* (noun, gender masculine) is derived from “Galvarino,” a famous Mapuche warrior who fought the invasion and attempt of servitude of the Mapuche people by the colonial Spaniards in Chile during the sixteenth century. The Mapuche are indigenous people from Chile and some parts of Argentina, who had most of their territory diminished by Spanish colonization. The name is in reference to the distribution of the genus type species

Galvarinus chilensis, restricted to Chile and Argentina...”]. *Galvarinus* Trevine, Grazziotin, Giraudo, Sallesbery-Pinchera, Vianna & Zaher, 2022. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Gambelia: Gambel + L. *-ia*, suffix denoting belonging to. Honouring William Gambel, Jr. (1823–1849) US explorer, naturalist and collector. *Gambelia* Baird, 1859. Sauria: Crotophytidae.

Garthia: Garth + L. *-ia*, dedicative suffix. Honouring Garth Leon Underwood (1919-2002), British herpetologist. *Garthia* Donoso-Barros & Vanzolini, 1965. Sauria: Phyllodactylidae.

Geagras: *G. gea* (from γῆ, γῆς), earth, land + *G. agreus* (ἀγρεύς), a hunter. [?]. *Geagras* Cope, 1876. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Gehyra: Unknown. Maybe from *G. gee* (γῆ-), from the earth + *G. gýra* (γυρὰ), rounded, curved, crooked. [?]. Possibly a meaningless but euphonious combination of letters, as Gray often produced. *Gehyra* Gray, 1834. Sauria: Gekkonidae.

Gekko: *L. gekko*, from Indonesian-Malaysian *gēkoq*, onomatopoeia of the sound made by these animals. [?]. The first reference on the onomato-

poetic origin of the name was given by Bontius (1658): “...Nostrates ipsum animal appposito vocabulo Gecco vocant; Quippe non secus, ac Coccyx apud nos suum cantum iterat; etiam Gecco assiduo sonat, pius edito stridore, qualem Picus emitit...”. *Gekko* Laurenti 1768. Sauria: Gekkonidae.

Gelanesaurus: *G. gelanes* (γελανής), cheerful + *G. sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [“...The name *Gelanesaurus* derives from the Greek words *gelanes* (=laughing, cheerful) and *sauros* (=lizard), and refers to the joker-looking head color pattern of the included species, more marked in *G. flavogularis*...”]. *Gelanesaurus* Torres-Carvajal, Lobos, Venegas, Chávez, Aguirre-Peñafiel, Zurita & Echevarría, 2016. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Geophis: *G. gea* (from γῆ, γῆς), earth, land + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Geophis* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Gerrhonotus: *G. gerron* (γέρρον), oblong shield; anything made of wicker-work + *G. notos* (νῶτος) the back; dorsum. [“...Caput pyrami datum, obtusum, clypeolis irregulari-multangulis tectum...”]. *Gerrhonotus* Wiegmann, 1828. Sauria: Anguillidae.

Glaucomastix: *G. glaucos* (γλαυκός), grey-blue or grey-green + *G. mastix* (μάστιξ), a whip, scourge. [... *Glaucomastix* is a composite name derived from the Greek adjectives “*glaucos*”, meaning blue-green, and “*mastix*”, meaning whip. The name alludes to the bluish-green tail that characterizes this group of lizards...]. *Glaucomastix* Goicoechea, Frost, De la Riva, Pellegrino, Sites, Rodrigues & Padial, 2016. Sauria: Teiidae.

Glyptemys: *G. glyptos* (γλυπτός), fit for carving + *G. emys* (έμυς), freshwater tortoise. [?]. *Glyptemys* Agassiz, 1857. Testudines: Emydidae.

Gomesophis: P. Gomes, family name + *G. ophis* (όφις), a serpent, snake. Honouring João Florêncio Gomes (1886-1919), Brazilian naturalist and descriptor of the type species *Gomesophis* Hoge & Mertens, 1959. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Gonatodes: *G. gonatodes* (γονατώδης), with joints. [?]. *Gonatodes* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Sphaerodactylidae.

Gopherus: *E. gopher*, perhaps an Anglicizing of Louisiana French *gaufre*, honeycomb, waffle, said to have been used by French settlers in reference to small mammals in

analogy to the structure of their burrows. [?]. *Gopherus* Rafinesque, 1832. Testudines: Testudinidae.

Graptemys: *G. graptos* (γραπτός), written down, written; marked with patterns resembling letters + *G. emys* (έμυς), a freshwater tortoise. [?]. *Graptemys* Agassiz, 1857. Testudines: Emydidae.

Gyalopion: *G. gyalon* (γύαλον), concavity; a hollow + *G. pion* (πίον), fat. [...Rostral plate acute; its anterior border elevated; its upper surface concave...]. *Gyalopion* Cope, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Gymnodactylus: *G. gymnos* (γυμνός), naked + *G. dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [...digitis omnibus liberis, non fimbriatis...]. *Gymnodactylus* Spix, 1825. Sauria: Phyllodactylidae.

Gymnophthalmus: *G. gymnos* (γυμνός), naked + *G. ophthalmos* (οφθαλμός), eye. [...Palpebrae nullae?...]. *Gymnophthalmus* Merrem, 1820. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Habrophallos: *G. abros* (άβρός), delicate, graceful, beautiful, pretty + *G. phallos* (φαλλός), membrum virile, phallus. [...The generic name is derived from the Greek “*habros*”

(pretty, graceful, delicate) + the Greek “*phallos*,” used herein in reference to the small, delicate, and diagnostic hemipenial morphology of the new genus...”. *Habrophallos* Martins, Koch, Pinto, Folly, Fouquet & Passos, 2020. Serpentes: Leptotyphlopidae.

***Helicops*:** *G. elikopis* (ἐλικῶπις), with lively eyes. *Helicops* Wagler, 1828. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Helminthophis*:** *G. helminthos* (ἑλμινθος), worm + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), serpent, snake. [“...Diese Wurmsschlange hat die abgerundete Schnauze und die seitlichen Augen...”]. *Helminthophis* Peters, 1860. Serpentes: Anomalepididae.

***Heloderma*:** *G. elos* (ἤλος), wart, callus + *G. derma* (δέρμα), skin, hide. [“...Truncus cute squamulosa, rugis transversis parallelis distincta vestitus, squamis majoribus distinctantibus tuberiformibus, osseis...”]. *Heloderma* Wiegmann, 1829. Sauria: Helodermatidae.

***Hemidactylus*:** *G. hemi-* (ἡμι-), half + *G. dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [“...Zehen dünn; die Sohlenscheibe oval, von einer doppelten Reihe von Blättchen gebildet...”]. *Hemidactylus* Goldfuss, 1820 (fide Frétey & Dubois 2019). Sauria: Gekkonidae.

***Hemiphyllodactylus*:** *L. Hemidactylus*, lizard genus due to Oken, 1817 (see) + *L. Phyllodactylus*, lizard genus due to Gray, 1828 (see). [“...Staat in verwantschap tusschen *Platydactylus* en *Hemidactylus*...”]. *Hemiphyllodactylus* Bleeker, 1860. Sauria: Gekkonidae.

***Heterodactylus*:** *G. heteros* (ἕτερος), of another kind, different + *G. dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [“...pedibus anterioribus 4-dactylis, posterioribus 5-dactylis...”]. *Heterodactylus* Spix, 1825. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Heterodon*:** *G. heteros* (ἕτερος), of another kind, different + *G. odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [“...Branche extérieure de la mâchoire supérieure ayant près de son origine deux dents plus longues. Point d’autres dents propres à être des crochets à venin...”]. *Heterodon* Latreille, 1801. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Holbrookia*:** Holbrook, a family name + *L. -ia*, or *G. -ia*, suffix denoting pertaining to. Honouring John Edwards Holbrook (1796-1871), US American herpetologist. *Holbrookia* Girard, 1851. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

***Holcosus*:** Unclear; perhaps from *L. holcus*, a kind of grain (Poaceae)

+ L. *-osus*, rich in; abounding in [?]. [“...Frontal, fronto-parietal and parietal plates very numerous...”]. *Holcosus* Cope, 1862. Sauria: Teiidae.

Homonota: G. *homos* (ὁμός), same, uniform, similar + G. *notos* (νωτος), back, dorsum. [“...scales of the back hexangular, smooth, scarcely imbricate...”]. *Homonota* Gray, 1845. Sauria: Phyllodactylidae.

Hoplocercus: G. *hoplos* (ὄπλον), implements of war, arms and armour + G. *cercos* (κέρκος) tail. [“...Cauda breviuscula, verticillata...”]. *Hoplocercus* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Hoplocercidae.

Hydrodynastes: G. *hydros* (ὑδρος), a water-snake + G. *dynastes* (δυναστής), a lord, master, ruler. [?]. *Hydrodynastes* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Hydromedusa: G. *hydor* (ὑδωρ), water + G. *medeon* (μεδέων) → *medeoussa* (μεδέουσα), ruling, holding. [“...Υδρομεδουσα, a ὑδωρ aqua, et μεδω imperio...”]. *Hydromedusa* Wagler, 1830. Testudines: Chelidae.

Hydromorphus: L. *Hydrus*, snake genus due to Schneider, 1799 (see

+ G. *morpho* (μορφή), form, shape. [“...Diese neue Gattung schließt sich durch die Körperform zunächst an die Homalopsidae mit ungefurchten hinteren Zähnen, *Calopisma*, *Hypsirhina* und *Hydrops* an, ist aber durch eigentümlichen Kieferbau, Bezahnung und Kopfschilder leicht zu unterscheiden...”]. *Hydromorphus* Peters, 1859. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Hydrophis: G. *hydor* (ὑδωρ), water + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...Hydrophis...”]. *Hydrophis* Latreille, 1801. Serpentes: Elapidae.

Hydrops: G. *hydros* (ὑδρος), a water-snake + G. *ops* (ὄψ, ὄψ), face, eye. [“...Υδρος, serpens aquaticus, et οψ facies...”]. *Hydrops* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Hypsiglena: G. *hypsi-* (ὑψι-), on high, aloft; to a high or relatively high position + G. *glenes* (γλήνη), the pupil of the eye, eyeball. [“...Pupil elliptic, erect...”]. *Hypsiglena* Cope, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Iguana: S. *iguana*, a lizard; from A. *iwana*, vernacular name for the species. [?]. [Probably the oldest printed mention of the name is that of Pedro Mártir de Anglería (1511), [“...las sierpes, a las que consideran en primer lugar entre sus alimentos,

y que describimos más arriba y son similares a los cocodrilos. A estas sierpes llaman *Iuanas...*”]. *Iguana Laurenti* 1768. Sauria: Iguanidae.

***Imantodes*:** G. *imantodes* (ἰμαντώδης), fibrous, leather-like. [“...Tronc à dos en carène...”]. *Imantodes* Duméril, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Incaspis*:** Q. *inka*, ruler, emperor + G. *aspis* (ἄσπις), asp, venomous snake. [“...The genus name is a combination of the Quechua word *Inca* (adjective, meaning royalty) and the Greek word *-aspis* (noun, ἄσπις, meaning venomous snake), in reference to the Andean region where the Inca Empire was established...”]. *Incaspis* Donoso-Barros, 1974. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Indotyphlops*:** L. *Indus*, *Indi*, Indian, inhabitant of India + G. *typhlops* (τυφλωψ), blind-eyed, blind. [“...The generic name is a masculine noun formed from the adjective *indianus* (a, um; i.e., ‘from India’) and the Greek noun *typhlops* (the blind)...”]. *Indotyphlops* Hedges, Marion, Lipp, Marin & Vidal, 2014. Serpentes: Typhlopidae.

***Iphisa*:** Unclear. Possibly from G. *Iphis* (Ἰφίς), daughter of Ligdus and Telethusa, or Ἰφίς, a slave of Pa-

troclus, or L. *Iphis*, one of the Argonauts, or from G. *iphios* (ἴφιος), stout, fat, goodly, or just an arbitrary combination of letters? [?]. *Iphisa* Gray, 1851. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Kaieteurosaurus*:** E. Kaieteur, a National Park in Guyana (in turn, from Pa. “the place where the old man fell” + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [“...The generic name is a noun in apposition and is derived from “Kaieteur” referring to the Kaieteur National Park where the type species occurs, the connecting -o, and the Greek “*saurus*” meaning “lizard”...”]. *Kaieteurosaurus* Kok, 2005. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Kataphraktosaurus*:** G. *kataphractus* (κατάφρακτος), shut up, confined + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [“...The generic name *Kataphraktosaurus* (gender masculine) is derived from the combination of the G. word κατάφρακτος (“*katáphraktos*”), which means completely enclosed, covered or armored, and the Neo-L. *-saurus*—derived from the ancient G. σαῦρος (“*saûros*”)—, which means lizard...”]. *Kataphraktosaurus* Rojas-Runjaic, Barrio-Amorós, Señaris, De la Riva & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2021. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Kentropyx: G. *kentroo* (κεντρόω), to furnish with a sting + G. *pyka* (πύκα), thickly, solidly. ["...aculeo utrinque ad anum oblongo..."]. *Kentropyx* Spix, 1825. Sauria: Teiidae.

Kinosternon: G. *cineo* (κινέω), to set in motion, to move + G. *sternon* (στέρνον) breast, chest. [?]. *Kinosternon* Spix, 1824. Testudines: Kinosternidae.

Lacerta: L. *lacerta*, Latin name for a lizard. ["...Corpus tetrapodum, caudatum, nudum..."]. The alusion to a naked body is striking, because the salamanders included were very few. *Lacerta* Linnaeus 1758. Sauria: Lacertidae.

Lachesis: G. *Lachesis* (Λάχεσις), in G. mythology, one of the three Fates. ["...Le nom d'une des Parques qui tenaient entre leurs mains le fil de nos destinées, selon l'expression des poètes anciens, peut convenir au nouveau genre d'ophidiens dont je vais donner la description, puisqu'il ne renferme que des animaux très redoutables par leur morsure envenimée et souvent mortelle.."]. *Lachesis* Daudin, 1803. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Laemanctus: G. *laimos* (λαιμός), throat, gullet + L. *arcto*, to squeeze,

compress. ["...iugulum constrictum, transverse plicatum..."]. *Laemanctus* Wiegmann, 1834. Sauria: Corytophanidae.

Lampropeltis: G. *lampros* (λαμπρός), bright, brilliant, radiant + G. *pelta* (πέλτη), small light shield of leather without a rim. [?]. *Lampropeltis* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Leiocephalus: G. *leios* (λείος), smooth, plain, not embroidered + G. *cephale* (κεφάλη), head. In the diagnosis of the type species, ["...capite glabro..."]. *Leiocephalus* Gray, 1827. Sauria: Leiocephalidae.

Leiosaurus: G. *leios* (λείος), smooth, plain, not embroidered + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. ["...De Λείος, lisse, uni, laevis, non scaber ; et de Σαῦρος, Lézard, Lacerta..."]. *Leiosaurus* Duméril & Bibron, 1837. Sauria: Leiosauridae.

Lepidoblepharis: G. *lepidos* (λεπίδος) a scale + G. *blepharon* (βλέφαρον), eyelid. ["...Palpebra inferiore rudimentale, la superiore laminare, sporgente all'esterno a mezzaluna, non chiudente l'occhio..."]. *Lepidoblepharis* Peracca, 1897. Sauria: Sphaerodactylidae.

Lepidochelys: G. *lepidos* (λεπίδος) collectively, the scales of fish or reptiles + G. *chelys* (χέλυς), turtle. [?]. *Lepidochelys* Fitzinger, 1843. Testudines: Cheloniidae.

Lepidodactylus: G. *lepidos* (λεπίδος) a scale + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [?]. *Lepidodactylus* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Gekkoniidae.

Lepidophyma: G. *lepidos* (λεπίδος) a scale + G. *phyma* (φῶμα), a growth, tubercle, wart, tumor. ["...Tronc revêtu en dessus et sur les flancs d'écaillés granuleuses, petites et très-serrées, entremêlées de tubercules coniques et pointus, beaucoup plus gros, disposés en séries transversales plus ou moins régulières..."]. *Lepidophyma* Duméril, 1851. Sauria: Xantusiidae.

Leposoma: G. *lepos* (λέπος), rind, husk, scale + G. *soma* (σῶμα), body. ["...squamis dorsis, nec non capitatis subasperis, acutis, medio carinatis..."]. *Leposoma* Spix, 1825. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Leposternon: G. *lepos* (λέπος), rind, husk, scale + G. *sternon* (στέρνον), breast, chest. ["...Caput et sternum scutata..."]. *Leposternon* Wagler, 1824. Sauria: Amphisbaenidae.

Leptodeira: G. *leptos* (λεπτός), fine, thin, delicate, subtle + G. *deira* (δειρή), neck, throat. [?]. *Leptodeira* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Leptodrymus: L. *Leptophis* snake genus due to Bell, 1825 (see) + L. *Drymobius*, snake genus due to Fitzinger, 1843 (see). ["...*Leptodrymus* is close to both *Drymobius* Fitzinger and *Leptophis* Wagler through its dentition, physiognomy, shape and pholidosis..."]. *Leptodrymus* Amaral, 1927. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Leptophis: G. *leptos* (λεπτός), fine, thin, delicate, subtle + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. ["...I propose to give the name *Leptophis* (from λεπτός gracilis and ὄφις serpens)..."]. *Leptophis* Bell, 1825. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Lichanura: G. *lichanos* (λιχανός), the fore-finger + G. *oura* (οὐρά), tail. ["...tail short, thick, obtuse at the extremity..."]. *Lichanura* Cope, 1861. Serpentes: Boidae.

Liodytes: G. *leios* (λείος), smooth, plain, not embroidered + G. *dytes* (δύτης), a diver. ["...I note here that the *Helicops alleni* Garman, from Florida, has the scales entirely smooth. It is necessary therefore that it be placed in another genus,

which I call *Liodytes*...”]. *Liodytes* Cope, 1885. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Lioheterophis*:** G. *leios* (λείος), smooth, plain, not embroidered + G. *heteros* (ἕτερος), of another kind, different + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Lioheterophis* Amaral, 1935. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Liolaemus*:** G. *leios* (λείος), smooth, plain, not embroidered + G. *laimos* (λαιμός), throat, gullet. [“...cuti gulari adstricta, plicae iugularis rudimento supra axillas...”]. *Liolaemus* Wiegmann, 1834. Sauria: Liolaemidae.

***Liotyphlops*:** G. *leios* (λείος), smooth, plain, not embroidered + G. *typhlos* (τυφλός), blind. [?]. *Liotyphlops* Peters, 1881. Serpentes: Anomalepididae.

***Loxocemus*:** G. *loxos* (λοξός), slanting + G. *cepos* (κημός), muzzle. [“...Muzzle prominent, obliquely truncate...”]. *Loxocemus* Cope, 1861. Serpentes: Loxocemidae.

***Loxopholis*:** G. *loxos* (λοξός), slanting + G. *pholis* (φολῖς), horny scale. [“...The scales imbricate, arranged in oblique rows or quincuncially...”]. *Loxopholis* Cope, 1869. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Lygodactylus*:** G. *lygoi* (λύγοι), pliant twigs of willow (used for binding or plaiting) + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [“...Toes free, all clawed, slender and sub-cylindrical...”]. *Lygodactylus* Gray, 1864. Sauria: Gekkonidae.

***Lygophis*:** G. *lygoi* (λύγοι), pliant twigs of willow (used for binding or plaiting) + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Lygophis* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Macrochelys*:** G. *makros* (μακρός), long in extent + G. *chelys* (χέλυς), tortoise. [“...Head large, angular...”]. *Macrochelys* Gray, 1856. Testudines: Chelydridae.

***Macropholidus*:** G. *makros* (μακρός), long in extent + G. *pholidos* (φολίδος), a horny scale. [“...Two medial rows of large hexagonal scales extending from occipital region to base of tail...”]. *Macropholidus* Noble, 1921. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Magdalenasaura*:** S. Magdalena, a Colombian river + G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [“...*Magdalenasaura* (gender feminine) derives from the Spanish word Magdalena and the Greek word *saura* (lizard), in allusion to the Magdalena River basin where the two species have

been found...”]. *Magdalenasaura* Fang, Vázquez-Restrepo & Daza, 2020. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Malaclemys: G. *malacos* (μαλακός), soft + G. *clemmys* (κλεμμύς), tortoise. [“...Head very large, depressed, covered with a soft spongy skin...”]. *Malaclemys* Gray, 1844. Testudines: Emydidae.

Manciola: L. *manciola*, dim. of *manus*, a little hand. [“...The generic name (*Manciola*) is a feminine, Latin, noun meaning small hand, in reference to the relatively small hands and feet in these skins...”]. *Manciola* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Manolepis: G. *manos* (μανός), loose, porous; few, scanty + G. *lepis* (λεπίς), a scale. [?]. *Manolepis* Cope, 1885. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Maracaiba: S. Maracaibo, lake and capital city of Zulia State, Venezuela. [“...The generic name (*Maracaiba*) is a feminine noun and refers to the distribution of the genus, centered around Lago de Maracaibo in northern Venezuela...”]. *Maracaiba* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Marinussaurus: D. Marinus, a given name + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. Honouring Marinus Steven Hoog-

moed (1942), Dutch-born Brazilian herpetologist active in Surinam and Brazil. *Marinussaurus* Peloso, Pellegrino, Rodrigues & Ávila-Pires, 2011. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Marisora: L. *maris*, sea + L. *ora*, coast, border. [“...The generic name (*Marisora*) is a feminine noun derived from the Latin words *maris* (sea) and *ora* (coast, or border), referring to the distribution of this genus occurring predominately in low elevations near the coast (Caribbean, Atlantic, and Pacific), with relatively few inland and upland localities. Three of the seven species occur exclusively on islands...”]. *Marisora* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Masticophis: G. *mastizo* (μαστίζω), a whip, scourge + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...Similar in general features to *Bascanion*, but still more slender and elongated. Tail very long...”]. *Masticophis* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Mastigodryas: L. *Masticophis*, snake genus due to Baird & Girard, 1853 (see) + L. *Eudryas*, snake genus due to Fitzinger, 1843. [“...este genero é affim de *Eudryas* Fitzinger e *Masticophis* Baird & Girard...”]. *Mastigodryas* Amaral, 1935. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Medopheos: *G. medea* (μήδεα), genitals + *G. pheos* (φέως), a thorny plant. [“... from the *G.* noun *medea* meaning genitalia and *pheos*, a term used to refer to certain spiny plants. The name alludes to the distinctive cluster of 5–6 preanal spurs on either side of the vent of males...”]. *Medopheos* Harvey, Ugueto & Gutberlet, 2012. Sauria: Teiidae.

Melanosuchus: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. souchos* (σοῦχος), crocodile. [“...Back black varied with yellow...”]. *Melanosuchus* Gray, 1862. Crocodylia: Alligatoridae.

Mesoamericus: *S.* Mesoamérica, cultural and geographical region of the Americas that encompasses Central America and southern Mexico + *L.* -us, having the nature of. [“... The generic name is a masculine noun derived from the name for the region (Mesoamerica) where it occurs...”]. *Mesoamericus* Schools & Hedges, 2021. Sauria: Diploglossidae.

Mesobaena: *G. mesos* (μέσος), of the middle point or part + *G. baino* (βαίνω), walk, step, but also of all motion on ground. [“...Diese südamerikanische Leposternidengattung steht zwischen Amphisbaena und Anopsibaena...”]. *Mesobaena*

Mertens, 1925. Sauria: Amphisbaenidae.

Mesoclemmys: *G. mesos* (μέσος), middle, in the middle + *G. clemmys* (κλεμμύς), tortoise. [“...This genus is between *Hydraspis* and *Platemys* in the form of the skull, but is known from both by the regular shields on the head...”]. *Mesoclemmys* Gray, 1873. Testudines: Chelidae.

Mesoscincus: *G. mesos* (μέσος), middle (of) + *L. Scincus*, reptile genus due to Laurenti (1768). [“...The name refers to the Middle American distribution of this group, and its current position as a middle group within the scincid cladogram. It is masculine in gender...”]. *Mesoscincus* Griffith, Ngo & Murphy, 2000. Sauria: Scincidae.

Mesotes: *G. mesotes* (μεσότης), a middle; state between two extremes. [?]. *Mesotes* Jan, 1863. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Metlapilcoatlus: *N. metlapilli*, from *N. metlatl* (metate) and *N. pilli* (son); a type of roller used for grinding on the metate + *N. coatl*, snake. [“...The generic name is derived from the náhuatl *metlapil*, referring to the thick mortar used with a grinding stone called metate,

and *coatl*, meaning “serpent.” ...”]. *Metlapilcoatlus* Campbell, Frost & Castoe, 2019. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Micrablepharus: *G. micros* (μῖκρός), small, little, short + *G. blepharon* (βλέφαρον), eyelid. [?. “...supraocularibus 2, altero maximo, altero minore...”]. *Micrablepharus* Boettger, 1885. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Microlophus: *G. micros* (μικρός), small, little, short + *G. lophos* (λόφος), neck, crest of hill, ridge, crest of a helmet. [“...De Μικρός, petite, *parva*, et λόφος, crête, *crista*...”]. *Microlophus* Duméril & Bibron, 1837. Sauria: Tropiduridae.

Micruroides: *L. Micrurus*, snake genus due to Wagler in Spix, 1824 (see) + *G. -oides* (-οειδής), suffix indicating likeness. [?]. *Micruroides* Schmidt, 1928. Serpentes: Elapidae.

Micrurus: *G. micros* (μικρός), small, little, short + *G. oura* (οὐρᾶ), tail. [“...Cauda brevissima...”]. *Micrurus* Wagler in Spix, 1824. Serpentes: Elapidae.

Mixcoatlus: *N. Mixcoatl*, god of the hunt or the cloud serpent; from *N. mixtli*, cloud and *N. coatl*, snake. [“...The generic name is derived

from the Náhuatl word *Mixcoatl*, meaning ‘cloud serpent’, a god of the Aztecs and several Mesoamerican civilizations. The name alludes to the restriction of this clade to high elevations. The gender of this name is masculine...”]. *Mixcoatlus* Jadin, Smith & Campbell, 2011. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Mussurana: *T. muçurana*, a rope used in ritual sacrifice; also, *T. muçu*, freshwater eel (Synbranchiformes) + *T. rana*, what seems like but is not the same. [“...From *Mosu-* (indigenous Tupi, “eel”) + *Rana* (indigenous Tupi, “like or false”), gender feminine (Amaral, 1974). *Mussurana* or *Muçurana* is a very common name in Latin America, applied mostly to the dark adults of pseudoboine snakes...”]. *Mussurana* Zaher, Graziotin, Cadle, Murphy, Moura-Leite & Bonatto, 2009. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Nerodia: *G. neros* (νηρός), flowing, liquid + *G. -ia* (-ία), suffix denoting belonging to. [“...Habits aquatic...”]. *Nerodia* Baird in Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Neusticurus: *G. neusticos* (νευστικός), able to swim + *G. oura* (οὐρᾶ), tail. [“...De *Νευστικός*, *nantans*, *natrix*, prope à nager et de οὐρᾶ, *cauda*, queue...”]. *Neusti-*

curus Duméril & Bibron, 1839.
Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Ninia: Unknown. McCranie (2011) speculates that *Ninia* might be derived from the English word nine and the Greek suffix *-ia* (pertaining to), in reference to the normal colubrid condition of having nine large scales on the dorsal surface of the head. *Ninia* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Nothobachia: G. *nothos* (νόθος), cross-bred; bastard + L. *Bachia*, lizard genus due to Gray, 1845. [?]. *Nothobachia* Rodrigues, 1984. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Nothopsis: G. *nothos* (νόθος), cross-bred; bastard + G. *opsis* (ὄψις), aspect, appearance. [...Its superficial characters remind one at once of the Peropoda, and the double urosteges suggest the Pythons...]. *Nothopsis* Cope, 1871. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Notomabuya: G. *notos* (νότος), the south + L. *Mabuya*, lizard genus due to Fitzinger, 1826. [...The generic name (*Notomabuya*) is a feminine noun derived from the Greek *notos* (south, southern) and *mabuya* (a Neotropical skink), hence “Southern Neotropical Skink,” in allusion to the distribution of the included

species (*frenata*) in southern South America...]. *Notomabuya* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Omoadiphas: S. [Sierra de] Omoa, a mountain range in the Cortés department, Honduras + G. *diphas* (δίφας), a kind of serpent. [...The genus name is derived from the name of the mountain range (Sierra de Omoa) containing the type locality, and the Greek *diphas*, meaning “a kind of serpent” (Brown 1991). The generic name is feminine...]. *Omoadiphas* Köhler, McCranie & Wilson, 2001. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Opheodrys: G. *opheodes* (ὀφειώδης), snake-like. [?]. *Opheodrys* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Ophiodes: G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake + G. *-oides* (-ειδής), suffix denoting likeness. [?]. *Ophiodes* Wagler, 1828. Sauria: Diploglossidae.

Ophisaurus: G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [?]. *Ophisaurus* Daudin, 1803. Sauria: Anguidae.

Ophryacus: G. *ophrys* (ὀφρὺς), eyebrow + G. *acis* (ἀκίς), a point, the barb of an arrow. [...This genus differs from *Bothrops* in the pro-

longation of one of the superciliary scales into a horn like process...”]. *Ophryacus* Cope, 1887. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Oreosaurus: G. *oreos* (ὄρεος), mountain, hill + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [In the characterization of its type species: “...Das Vaterland dieser Art ist Neu Granada; acht Exemplare zum Theil in verstümmeltem Zustande, hat das zoologische Museum aus den Hochgebirgen in der Umgebung von Sta Fé de Bogotá erhalten...”]. *Oreosaurus* Peters, 1863. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Oxybelis: G. *oxybelis* (ὄξυβελής), sharp-pointed- [“...ὄξυβελής acutum cuspidem gerens...”]. *Oxybelis* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Oxyrhopus: G. *oxyrropos* (ὄξύρροπος), turning quickly. [“...ὄξύρροπος qui celeriter repit...”]. *Oxyrhopus* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Paikwaophis: [?]. Paikwa, a river in Cuyuni-Mazaruni Region, Guyana + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...The generic name is derived from the river name ‘Paikwa’ (referring to the type locality) and the Greek ‘*ophis*’ (meaning snake)...”]. *Paikwaophis* Kok & Means, 2023. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Palea: L. *palea*, chaff, husk; the wattles or gills of a cock. [“...From the L. *palea*, meaning wattles, in reference to the autapomorphic structures on the neck...”]. *Palea* Meylan, 1987. Testudines: Trionychidae.

Paleosuchus: G. *palaios* (παλαιός), old, aged, ancient + G. *souchos* (σοῦχος), crocodile. [?]. *Paleosuchus* Gray, 1862. Crocodylia: Alligatoridae.

Palusophis: L. *palus*, a swamp, marsh, morass, bog, fen, pool + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...From the Latin word *Palus* (swamp, marsh), and the Greek *ophis* (serpent) in reference to the habitat of its species, *Palusophis bifossatus*, in humid areas of both forested and open environments in South America...”]. *Palusophis* Montingelli, Grazziotin, Battilana, Murphy, Zhang & Zaher, 2019. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Panopa: G. *pan* (πᾶν, from πᾶς), all, the whole + G. *loras* (λοπάς), a flat dish. [“...The generic name (*Panopa*) is a feminine noun and is derived from the Greek adjective *pan* (whole, undivided) and noun *loras* (flat plate), in allusion to the single (fused) frontoparietal scale...”]. *Panopa* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Pantepuisaurus: SL. *Pantepui*, biogeographic province in the mountains ('tepuis') of the Guiana Region above 1,200 to 1,500 m a.s.l. + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. ["...A noun in apposition, derived from "Pantepui" referring to the phytogeographic province where the type species was discovered, and the Greek *sauros* meaning "lizard". Gender masculine..."]. *Pantepuisaurus* Kok, 2009. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Pantherophis: G. *panther* (πάνθηρ), the panther + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Pantherophis* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Paraphimophis: G. *para* (παρά), besides, near + L. *Phimophis*, snake genus due to Cope, 1860. ["... From the Greek "para" and *Phimophis*, meaning near the genus *Phimophis*..."]. *Paraphimophis* Zaher, Grazziotin, Murphy, Scrocchi, Altamirano, Benavides, Zhang & Bonatto in Grazziotin et al. 2012. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Pelodiscus: G. *pelos* (πηλός), mud, mire + L. *discus*, disk/disc; disk-shaped object. [?]. *Pelodiscus* Fitzinger, 1835. Testudines: Trionychidae.

Peltocephalus: G. *pelto* (πέλτη), small wooden or wicker shield with covering of skin; light shield + G. *cephale* (κεφαλή), head. ["... Nous répétons ici que nous avons cherché à indiquer, par ce nom de Peltocéphale, la disposition particulière des écailles qui recouvrent le crâne comme une sorte de casque, de πέλτη, un écusson, et de κεφαλή, tête..."]. *Peltocephalus* Duméril & Bibron, 1835. Testudines: Podocnemididae.

Petracola: L. *petra*, petra, a rock, crag, stone + L. *-cola*, dwelling in, inhabiting, living among. ["...*Petracola* is a masculine word derived from Latin, meaning rock dweller. It refers to the fact that these lizards are usually found beneath rocks on the ground..."]. *Petracola* Boulenger, 1900. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Petrosaurus: L. *petra*, petra, a rock, crag, stone + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [?]. *Petrosaurus* Boulenger, 1885. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

Phalotris: G. *phalos* (φάλος), horn of a helmet + G. *-tris* (τρίς), thrice, thrice as much or many. [?]. *Phalotris* Cope, 1862. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Phelsuma: D. Phelsum, a family name + L. *-a*, Latinizing suffix. Honour-

ing Murk van Phelsum (1732-1779), Dutch physician. *Phelsuma* Gray, 1825. Sauria: Gekkonidae.

Philodryas: G. *philos* (φίλος), loved, beloved, dear + G. *dryas* (δρυάς), (ref. to a nymph) inhabitant of trees. ["...Φίλος amicus, et δρυάς Sylvae Nympha (Ovid)..."]. *Philodryas* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Phimophis: G. *phimos* (φιμός), nose, muzzle; any instrument for keeping the mouth closed + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Phimophis* Cope, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Pholidobolus: G. *pholidoo* (φολιδόω), covered with horny scales + G. *bolis* (βολίς), a javelin, or G. *ballo* (βαλλο), to throw. *Pholidobolus* Peters, 1863. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Phrynonax: G. *phrynonos* (φρυωνος), like a toad. [?]. *Phrynonax* Cope, 1862. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Phrynops: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + G. *ops* (ὄψ, ὄψ), eye, face, countenance. ["...Φρύνος bufo, et ὄψ vultus..."]. *Phrynops* Wagler, 1830. Testudines: Chelidae.

Phrynosoma: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + G. *soma* (σῶμα), body. ["...Corpus compactile, bufonium..."]. *Phrynosoma* Wiegmann, 1828. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

Phyllodactylus: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. ["...Digiti 5-5 graciles compressi, ultimo articulo squamâ latâ foliacea longitudinaliter fissa..."]. *Phyllodactylus* Gray, 1828. Sauria: Phyllodactylidae.

Phyllopezus: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *pezos* (πεζός), on foot, on land. ["...φύλλον, πεζός..."]. *Phyllopezus* Peters, 1878. Sauria: Phyllodactylidae.

Phyllorhynchus: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *rhygchos* (ρύγχος), snout, beak. ["...rostral plate greatly enlarged, with free lateral borders, and produced backwards so as to separate the supranasals entirely..."]. *Phyllorhynchus* Stejneger, 1890. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Phymaturus: G. *phyma* (φῦμα), a growth: esp. a tumour + G. *oura* (οὐρά), tail. ["...Nach dieser Beschaffenheit des Schwanzes habe ich der Gattung den Namen Phymaturus, Beulenschwanz, gegeben, welcher aus den griechischen

Wörtern φῦμα Beule, und οὐρᾶ Schwanz, gebildet ist...”]. *Phymaturus* Gravenhorst, 1838. Sauria: Liolaemidae.

Pituophis: *G. pituoeis* (πιτυόεις), abounding in pine-trees + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...To Dr. S. Barker of South Carolina, I am indebted for many living specimens of the Serpents of the lower section of the state, and especially for a magnificent specimen of the *Pituophis melanoleucus*, or Pine Snake...”]. *Pituophis* Holbrook, 1842. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Placosoma: *G. placos* (πλάκος, from πλάξ), anything flat and broad + *G. soma* (σῶμα), body. [“...*Cervix integra. Dorsum integrum* ...”]. *Placosoma* Tschudi, 1847. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Platemys: *G. platus* (πλατύς), flat, wide, broad + *G. emys* (ἐμύς), freshwater tortoise. [“...Πλατυς, planus, et εμυς testudo...”]. *Platemys* Wagler, 1830. Testudines: Chelidae.

Plesiodipsas: *G. plesios* (πλήσιος), near, close to + *L. Dipsas*, snake genus due to Laurenti, 1768 (see). [“...The new name is a feminine noun formed by adding the prefix *plesio-* (derived from the Greek

word *plesios* meaning near) to the generic name *Dipsas* (derived from the Greek word for thirst)...”]. *Plesiodipsas*, Harvey Rivas-Fuenmayor Portilla & Rueda-Almonacid, 2008. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Plestiodon: *G. pleistos* (πλειστός), most, greatest, largest; the greatest number, the most + *G. odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [“...Πλειστός, plurimi, beaucoup; ὀδών- ὀδόντος, dentes, dents...”]. *Plestiodon* Duméril & Bibron, 1839. Sauria: Scincidae.

Plica: *L. plica*, fold. [“...collo lateribus verrucoso subtus plicato...”]. *Plica* Gray in Cuvier, 1831. Sauria: Tropiduridae.

Pliocercus: *G. pleon* (πλήων, from πλείων), more; most + *G. cercos* (κέρκος) tail. [“...The great length of the tail separates this genus from *Lampropeltis* and *Erythrolamprus*...”]. *Pliocercus* Cope, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Podarcis: *G. podarcis* (ποδαρκής), swift-footed. [“...Ποδαρκής pedibus celer...”]. *Podarcis* Wagler, 1830. Sauria: Lacertidae.

Podocnemis: *G. podos* (ποδός), from *G. pous* (πούς), foot + *G. cnemis* (κνημίς), greave or piece of armour

from knee to ankle. [...Πες pes, et κνημῖς ocrea...]. *Podocnemis* Wagler, 1830. Testudines: Podocnemididae.

Polychrus: G. *polys* (πολύς), much, many + G. *chroma* (χρώμα), the colour of the skin. [...ils jouissent, comme les caméléons, de la faculté de changer de couleur...]. *Polychrus* Cuvier, 1816. Sauria: Polychrotidae.

Porthidium: G. *portheo* (πορθέω), to destroy, ravage, waste, plunder + G. *-idion* (-ίδιον), diminutive suffix. [?]. *Porthidium* Cope, 1871. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Potamites: G. *potamites* (ποταμίτης), water-finder. [...*Potamites* is a masculine Greek noun, meaning water-finder. It refers to the fact that most members of this genus are semiaquatic, walking on the bottom of streams and often diving into streams to escape predation...]. *Potamites* Doan & Castoe, 2005. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Pristidactylus: G. *pristes* (πρίστης), saw or file + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [?]. *Pristidactylus* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Leiosauridae.

Procellosaurinus: L. *procella*, a violent wind, storm, hurricane, tempest + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard + G. *-inos* (-ινος), suffix indicating of, made of. [...O nome, que indica lagarto das regiões de ventos intensos ou uivantes, é dado em alusão às imensas dunas continentais onde suas espécies são encontradas...]. *Procellosaurinus* Rodrigues, 1991. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Proctoporus: G. *proctos* (προκτός), anus + G. *poros* (πόρος), pore; crossing-place. [...Pori anales per seriem semilunarem in ani margine posteriore dispositi...]. *Proctoporus* Tschudi, 1845. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Pseudalsophis: G. *pseudos* (ψευδης), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Alsophis*, snake genus due to Fitzinger, 1843. [...Pseudo- (Greek, “false, erroneous”) + *Alsophis*, in allusion to the morphological similarity with *Alsophis* Fitzinger sensu stricto, gender masculine...]. *Pseudalsophis* Zaher, Grazziotin, Cadle, Murphy, Moura-Leite & Bonatto, 2009. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Pseudelaphe: G. *pseudos* (ψευδης), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Elaphe*, snake genus due to Wagler, 1833. Beltz 2006 stated that *Elaphe* derives from G. *elaphos* (ἔλαφος), deer, as a misnomer, presumably

indicating swiftness. *Pseudelaphe* Mertens & Rosenberg, 1943. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Pseudemys*:** G. *pseudos* (ψευδης), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Emys*, chelonian genus due to Duméril 1805 (see). [?]. *Pseudemys* Gray, 1856. Testudines: Emydidae.

***Pseudoboa*:** G. *pseudos* (ψευδης), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Boa*, snake genus due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see). [“...Systematici plerisque cum *Bois* confusas propter scuta subcaudalia enarrarunt...”]. *Pseudoboa* Schneider, 1801. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Pseudoeryx*:** G. *pseudos* (ψευδης), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Eryx*, snake genus due to Daudin, 1803. [?]. *Pseudoeryx* Fitzinger, 1826. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Pseudoficimia*:** G. *pseudos* (ψευδης), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Ficimia*, snake genus due to Gray 1849. [?]. *Pseudoficimia* Bocourt, 1883. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Pseudogonatodes*:** G. *pseudos* (ψευδης), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Gonatodes*, lizard genus due to Fitzinger, 1843 (see). [?]. *Pseudogonatodes* Ruthven, 1915. Sauria: Sphaerodactylidae.

***Pseudoleptodeira*:** G. *pseudos* (ψευδης), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Leptodeira*, snake genus due to Fitzinger, 1843 (see). [?]. *Pseudoleptodeira* Taylor, 1938. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Psilops*:** G. *psilos* (ψιλῶς), naked, bare, stripped + G. *ops* (ὄψ, ὄψ), face, eye. [“...Pálpebra ausente...”]. *Psilops* Rodrigues, Recoder, Teixeira Jr, Roscito, Camacho Guerrero, Sales Nunes, Freitas, Silva Fernandes, Bocchiglieri, Dal Vechio, Fortes Leite, Campos Nogueira, Damasceno, Machado Pellegrino, Suzart Argôlo & Amaro, 2017. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

***Psomophis*:** G. *psomos* (ψωμός), a morsel, bit + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. [“...From the Greek *psomos* (a morsel or bit) + *ophis* (snake), alluding to the minuteness of these snakes, which doubtless are preyed on by many larger animals. Gender masculine...”]. *Psomophis* Myers & Cadle, 1994. Serpentes: Colubridae.

***Psychosaura*:** G. *psyche* (ψυχή), soul + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [“...The generic name (*Psychosaura*) is a feminine noun from the Greek *psyche* (mind) and *saura* (lizard), meaning “thinking lizard,” in allusion to the prominent heads, gracile bodies, and agile, active habits of the species...”]. *Psychosaura* Hed-

ges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Ptychophis: G. *ptych* (πτύχ), a fold, leaf, plate + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Ptychophis* Gomes, 1915. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Ranacephala: L. *rana*, frog + G. *cephale* (κεφαλή), head. [...Latin, *rana* for “frog,” and Greek, *cephale* for “head.” The “Froghead Turtle.”...]. *Ranacephala* McCord, Joseph-Ouni & Lamar, 2001. Testudines: Chelidae.

Regina: L. *regina*, a queen. [?]. *Regina* Baird in Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Rena: Presumably after L. *ren* (kidney), apparently in allusion to the kidney color (reddish brown) of the type species. [?]. *Rena* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Leptotyphlopidae.

Rhachidelus: G. *rachis* (ράχις), backbone, spine + G. *delos* (δῆλος), clear, visible. [...the scales being in 25 rows, those of the vertebral row distinctly enlarged...]. *Rhachidelus* Boulenger, 1908. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Rhachisaurus: G. *rachis* (ράχις), backbone, spine + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [...from Greek ‘*rhachis*’, an allusion to ‘Espinhaço’ (backbone), a single-word reference for the Portuguese noun ‘Serra do Espinhaço’, an extensive mountain range of eastern Brazil from where most specimens of *Rhachisaurus brachylepis* are known...]. *Rhachisaurus* Pellegrino, Rodrigues, Yonenaga-Yassuda & Sites, 2001. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Rhadinaea: G. *rhadinós* (ραδινός), slender, taper + L. *-ea*, feminine suffix. [...The general form is rather more slender...]. *Rhadinaea* Cope, 1863. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Rhadinella: L. *Rhadinaea*, snake genus due to Cope, 1863 (see) + L. *-ella*, suffix diminutive. [... From *Rhadinaea* it differs in its smaller size, short tail...]. *Rhadinella* Smith, 1941. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Rhadinophanes: G. *rhadinós* (ραδινός), slender, taper + G. *phaino* (φαίνω), show, cause to appear. [...From the Greek ραδινός (= *rhadinós*, slender, graceful) + the suffix φανεσ (= *phanes*, appearing), alluding both to the slenderness of the type species and to its superficial similarity to *Rhadinaea* and *Coniophanes*. Gender masculine...]. *Rhadinophanes* Myers &

Campbell, 1981. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Rheosaurus: G. *rheo* (ρέω), flow, stream + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [...The genus name *Rheosaurus* (gender masculine) is derived from the Greek ρέω, *rheo* (flow or stream) and σαύρα, *saura* (lizard), in reference to the riparian habit of this lizard...]. *Rheosaurus* Vásquez-Restrepo, Ibáñez, Sánchez-Pacheco & Daza, 2019. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Rhinemys: G. *rhinos* (ῥινός, genitive of ῥίς), nose, snout + G. *emys* (ἐμῦς), freshwater tortoise. [...Ῥίς nasus, et ἐμῦς testudo...]. *Rhinemys* Wagler, 1830. Testudines: Chelidae.

Rhineura: G. *rhin* (ῥίνη), file, rasp + G. *oura* (οὐρά), tail. [...It differed from both (and *Lepidosternum*) in the depressed, superiorly tuberculous tail...]. *Rhineura* Cope, 1861. Sauria: Rhineuridae.

Rhinobothryum: G. *rhinos* (ῥινός, genitive of ῥίς), nose, snout + G. *bothryon* (βοθρίον), small trench. [...ῥίς nasus, βοθρίον, fovea...]. *Rhinobothryum* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Rhinocheilus: G. *rhinos* (ῥινός, genitive of ῥίς), nose, snout + G. *cheilos* (χείλος), lip. [...Head subelliptical, pointed on the snout...]. *Rhinocheilus* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Rhinoclemmys: G. *rhinos* (ῥινός, genitive of ῥίς), nose, snout + G. *clemmys* (κλεμμύς), tortoise. [...Nasus protractus...]. *Rhinoclemmys* Fitzinger, 1836. Testudines: Geoemydidae.

Riama: Unknown. *Riama* Gray, 1858. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Riolama: Pemon-like name, *Riolama* is a fictional locality in the novel *Green Mansions*, by William Henry Hudson. [...Riolama was the name and home of Rima, who inhabited another isolated mountain of northern South America in W. H. Hudson's *Green Mansions*...]. *Riolama* Uzzell, 1973. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Rodriguesophis: P. Rodrigues, a family name + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. Honouring Miguel Trefaut Urbano Rodrigues (1953-) Brazilian herpetologist. *Rodriguesophis* Zaher, Grazziotin, Murphy, Scrocchi, Benavides, Zhang & Bonatto, 2012. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Rondonops: P. Rondon, a family name + L. *ops*, power, might; influence: Honouring Cândido Mariano da Silva Rondon (1865-1958), Brazilian military officer and explorer. *Rondonops* Colli, Hoogmoed, Cannatella, Cassimiro, Gomes, Ghellere, Sales Nunes, Pellegrino, Salerno, Marques de Souza & Rodrigues, 2015. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Salvadora: Unknown. There are several theories about the origin of this name. Perhaps from S. *Salvadora*, or L. *salvator*, savior + L. *adora*, honor, an explicit homage to the collector of the type species *S. grahamiae*, Col. J.D. Graham (fide Hernández-Jiménez et al. 2021). Alternatively, from L. *salvos*, sound or well preserved + L. *dura*, tough or outer covering, in reference to the smooth, tough skin. *Salvadora* Baird in Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Salvator: L. *salvator*, savior; latinization of the French *Sauvegarde*. [...Ve Genre SAUVEGARDE...]. *Salvator* Duméril & Bibron, 1839. Sauria: Teiidae.

Saphenophis: G. *saphenes* (σαφηνής), the plain truth + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [...From the G. *saphenes* (evident truth, clear) + *ophis* (a serpent), meaning ‘clearly a snake’...]. *Sa-*

phenophis Myers, 1973. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Sauromalus: G. *saura* (σαύρα), lizard + G. *omalos* (ὀμαλός), even, level. [...L’un des caractères remarquables de ce genre se tire de l’aplatissement du tronc, d’où le nom par lequel je propose de le désigner et qui est formé des mots grecs σαῦρος, lézard, et ὀμαλός, plat...]. *Sauromalus* Duméril, 1856. Sauria: Iguanidae.

Scaphiodontophis: G. *scapheion* (σκαφεῖον), spade, hoe, mattock + G. *odontotos* (οδοντωτος), furnished with teeth + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [...Maxillary teeth numerous (more than 50), the teeth scaphoid or spatulate...]. *Scaphiodontophis* Taylor & Smith, 1943. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Sceloporus: G. *scelos* (σκέλος), leg + G. *poros* (πόρος), pore; crossing-place. [...pori femorales magni...]. *Sceloporus* Wiegmann, 1828. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

Scincella: L. *Scincus*, lizard genus due to Laurenti (1768) + L. *-ella*, diminutive suffix. [...Small scincid lizards...]. *Scincella* Mittleman, 1950. Sauria: Scincidae.

Scolecophis: *G. scolex* (σκώληξ), a worm + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Scolecophis* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Scriptosaura: *L. scriptor*, writer, author; scribe + *L. saura* (from *G. σαύρα*), lizard. [...From the Latin “*scriptor*” = writer, and “*saura*” = lizard in reference to the sand tracks left by this sand swimming species. The tracks are in the origin of its popular name (escrivão = public writer) which is also attributed to other similar sand swimming lizards like those of the related genera *Calyptommatus* and *Nothobachia*...]. *Scriptosaura* Rodrigues & Maranhão dos Santos, 2008. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Selvasaura: *S. selva*, forest + *G. saura* (σαύρα), lizard. [...The generic name *Selvasaura* is derived from the Spanish noun ‘selva’ (forest) and the Greek noun σαύρα (lizard; *saura* is the feminine form) and refers to the habitat (montane rainforest) of the type species...]. *Selvasaura* Moravec, Šmid, Štundl & Lehr, 2018. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Seminatrix: *L. semi-*, half, partly + *L. Natrix*, snake genus due to Laurenti, 1768. [...An examination of the penial structure shows that the ref-

erence to the Natricinae is correct. The other characters differ, however, from those of the genus *Natrix*, so that it appears to be necessary to refer it to a new genus...]. *Seminatrix* Cope, 1895. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Senticolis: *L. sentis*, a thorn, thornbush, brier, bramble + *L. colis*, penis. [...The name *Senticolis* is from the Latin *sentis*, a thorn or bramble, and *colis*, a penis, in reference to the large spines on the hemipenis—perhaps the most distinctive morphological feature of this genus...]. *Senticolis* Dowling & Fries, 1986. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Siagonodon: *G. siagon* (σιαγών), jawbone, jaw + *G. odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [?]. *Siagonodon* Peters, 1881. Serpentes: Leptotyphlopidae.

Sibon: *L. sibina*, or *G. σιβύνη*, a hunting spear, a spear, pike. [?]. *Sibon* Fitzinger, 1826. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Siderolamprus: *G. sideros* (σίδηρος), iron + *G. lampros* (λαμπρός), bright, brilliant, radiant. [?]. *Siderolamprus* Cope, 1861. Sauria: Diploglossidae.

Simophis: G. *simos* (σιμός), snub-nosed, flat-nosed G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...σιμός, ὄφις...”]. *Simophis* Peters, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Siphlophis: G. *siphlos* (σιφλός), crippled, maimed G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Siphlophis* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Sistrurus: G. *seistron* (σεῖστρον), rattle + G. *oura* (οὐρᾶ), tail. [“...The name proposed for the species grouped under *Crotalophorus* of Gray, Holbrook, and others, but not of Linné or Gronow, is *Sistrurus* (σεῖστρον, a rattle)...”]. *Sistrurus* Garman, 1884. Serpentes: Viperidae.

Sonora: S. Sonora, a state in NW Mexico. [“...Sonora, Mex. ...”]. *Sonora* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Sordellina: Sordelli, a family name + L. *-ina*, feminine suffix sometimes with diminutive implications. Honouring Ferdinando Sordelli (1837-1916), Italian botanist and herpetologist. *Sordellina* Procter, 1923. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Sphaerodactylus: G. *sphaira* (σφαῖρα), any globe, sphere + G.

dactylos (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [“...Digiti simplices in discum, subtus laevem, integrum...”]. *Sphaerodactylus* Wagler, 1830. Sauria: Sphaerodactylidae.

Sphenomorphus: G. *sphenos* (σφηνός), wedge + G. *morpha* (μορφά), bodily form, build. [?]. *Sphenomorphus* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Scincidae.

Spilotes: G. *spilos* (σπίλος), a spot, stain + G. *-otes* (-οτης), suffix often used in Greek to form adjectives or nouns that denote a characteristic or association. [“...Fleckennatter...”]. *Spilotes* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Staurotypus: G. *stauros* (σταυρός), cross, as the instrument of crucifixion + G. *typos* (τύπος), form, shape. [“...Kreuzemyde ... Σταυροτυπυς crucis formam gerens...”]. *Staurotypus* Wagler, 1830. Testudines: Kinosternidae.

Stenocercus: G. *steno* (στενο), narrow, tight + G. *cercos* (κέρκος) tail. [“...de grandes écailles épineuses verticillées le long de la queue qui est comprimée...”]. *Stenocercus* Duméril & Bibron, 1837. Sauria: Tropicuridae.

Stenolepis: G. *steno* (στενο), narrow, tight + G. *lepis* (λεπίς), a scale. ["... Dorsal and lateral scales equal, hexagonal-lanceolate, keeled, imbricate, arranged in regular transverse series..."]. *Stenolepis* Boulenger, 1887. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Stenorrhina: G. *steno* (στενο), narrow, tight + G. *rhinos* (ῥινός), from (ῥίς), nose. ["... Orifices des narines percés dans une seule plaque..."]. *Stenorrhina* Duméril, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Sternotherus: G. *sternon* (στέρνον), breast, chest + *thairos* (θαίρος), hinge or pivot of a door. ["...the anterior lobe moveable, separated by a transverse ligamentous hinge..."]. *Sternotherus* Gray, 1825. Testudines: Kinosternidae.

Storeria: Storer, a family name + L. *-ia*, or G. *-ia*, suffix denoting pertaining to. Honouring David Humphreys Storer (1804-1891), US American physician and naturalist. *Storeria* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Strobilurus: G. *stobilos* (στροβιλός), spinning, whirling + G. *oura* (οὐρά), tail. ["...Cauda mediocris, compressiuscula, squamis maximis, carinatis, imbricatis, spiniferis..."]. *Strobilurus* Wiegmann, 1834. Sauria: Tropiduridae.

Symphimus: G. *symphyas* (συμφυάς), a growing together, connexion by natural growth + G. *-imos* (-ιμος), pertaining to, having the quality of. ["...cephalic plates normal except that the internasals are confluent with the nasal, and the latter with each other and with the loreal..."]. *Symphimus* Cope, 1869. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Sympholis: G. *syn* (σύν), in company with, together with + G. *pholis* (φολίς), horny scale. ["...its nasal confluent with with the first superior labial..."]. *Sympholis* Cope, 1861. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Synophis: G. *syn* (σύν), together; denoting joining, union, contact, proximity + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. ["...prefrontali uniti in un largo scudetto..."]. *Synophis* Peracca, 1896. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tachymenis: G. *tachys* (ταχύς), quick, swift + G. *menis* (μῆνις), wrath, anger. [?]. *Tachymenis* Wiegmann, 1835. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tachymenoides: L. *Tachymenis*, snake genus due to Wiegmann, 1835 (see) + L. *oides*, resembling, having the form of. ["...the suffix *-oides* (Greek: "similar," "likeness") indicates the historical proximity of this

taxon to *Tachymenis*, in reference to the type species description...”. *Tachymenoides* Trevine, Grazziotin, Giraudo, Sallesbery-Pinchera, Vianna & Zaher, 2022. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Taeniophallus: L. *taenia*, a band, hair-band, ribbon, fillet + L. *phallus*, from G. φαλλός, membrum virile, phallus. [?]. *Taeniophallus* Cope, 1895. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tantalophis: G. *Tantalos* (Τάνταλος), king of Phrygia, ancestor of the Pelopidae + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [“...The generic name comes from the Greek Τάνταλος, a mythological character symbolic of eternal torment, and from the Greek ὄφις for snake...”]. *Tantalophis* Duellman, 1958. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tantilla: L. *tantillus*, so little a thing, such a little thing. [?]. *Tantilla* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tantillita: L. *tantillita*, diminutive of *tantillus*, so small. [“...size small; tail relatively short...”]. *Tantillita* Smith, 1940. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tarentola: Ancient I. *tarantola*, salamander, from *Tarentum* (today Taranto), a city port of Greek origin

on the coast of southern Italy. [?]. *Tarentola* Gray, 1825. Sauria: Phyllodactylidae.

Teius: T., Gu. *teyu*, lizard. [“...Teju...”]. *Teius* Merrem, 1820. Sauria: Teiidae.

Terrapene: E. *terrapene*, from Powhatan (Pw.) *torope*, variety of turtle. [“...Terrapine...”]. *Terrapene* Merrem, 1820. Testudines: Emydidae.

Thamnodynastes: G. *thamnos* (θάμνος), bush, thicket, shrub + G. *dynastes* (δυναστής), a lord, master, ruler. [“...θάμνος frutex, et δυνασ[τ]. ἥς dominus...”]. *Thamnodynastes* Wagler, 1830. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Thamnophis: G. *thamnos* (θάμνος), bush, thicket, shrub + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Thamnophis* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Thecadactylus: G. *theca* (θήκη) case, chest + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. [“...Zehen ihrer ganzen Länge nach vor gleicher Breite. Die Sohlenscheiben durch eine tiefe Längsfurche getheilt, in welche sich die Nägel zurücklegen...”]. *Thecadactylus* Goldfuss, 1820. Sauria: Phyllodactylidae.

Tomodon: G. *tomos* (τόμος), a cut, slice + G. *odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [“...dents cannelées encore plus longues...”]. *Tomodon* Duméril, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Trachemys: G. *trachys* (τραχύς), jagged, rough, harsh, savage + G. *emys* (ἐμύς), freshwater tortoise. [“...and, finally, longitudinal ridges and rugosities prevail upon the scales...”]. *Trachemys* Agassiz, 1857. Testudines: Emydidae.

Trachylepis: G. *trachys* (τραχύς), jagged, rough, harsh, savage + G. *lepis* (λεπίς), a scale. [?]. *Trachylepis* Fitzinger, 1843. Sauria: Scincidae.

Tretanorhinus: G. *tretos* (τρητός), perforated, with a hole in it + G. *ano* (ἄνω), upwards, high above + G. *rhinos* (ρίνός, genitive of ῥίς), nose, snout. [“...De Τρητός, percé, perforatus, ἄνω en dessus, *superne*, et ῥίς nez, *nasus*. Narines percées au dessus du museau...”]. *Tretanorhinus* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tretioscincus: G. *tretos* (τρητός), perforated, with a hole in it + L. *Scincus*, lizard genus due to Laurenti, 1768 (see). [“...The discovery of this little lizard is particularly

interesting, as exhibiting femoral pores for the first time among the Scincidae...”]. *Tretioscincus* Cope, 1862. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Trilepida: G. *tri-* (τρι'), three + G. *lepidos* (λεπίδος) a scale. [“...I propose the new generic name *Trilepida* (from classical Greek; feminine; “three scales”) to continue allusion to the character (presence of three supralabials) which is useful—in combination with other traits (brown or pale brown venter, usually 10 midtail scales, moderate anterior supralabials)—in diagnosing the group...”]. *Trilepida* Hedges, 2011. Serpentes: Leptotyphlopidae.

Trimetopon: G. *tri-* (τρι'), three + G. *metopon* (μέτωπον), the space between the eyes, the brow, forehead. [“...Two internasals; one prefrontal plate...”]. *Trimetopon* Cope, 1885. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Trimorphodon: G. *tri-* (τρι'), three + G. *morpha* (μορφή), bodily form, build + G. *odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [“...Posterior superior maxillary tooth separate, grooved ; median teeth small ; anterior elongate, spaced...”]. *Trimorphodon* Cope, 1861. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Trioceros: G. *tri-* (τρι'), three + G. *ceras* (κέρας), the horn of an animal. [...General structure of Chamelion; but there are three long conical slightly curved horns, pointing forwards, before the eyes..."]. *Trioceros* Swainson, 1839. Sauria: Chamaeleonidae.

Tropidoclonion: G. *tropizo* (τροπιζω), furnish with a keel + G. *clonion* (κλωνιον, diminutive of κλών), a twig, spray. [?]. *Tropidoclonion* Cope, 1860. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tropidodipsas: G. *tropizo* (τροπιζω), furnish with a keel + L. *Dipsas*, a snake genus due to Laurenti, 1768 (see). [...scales moderate, keeled, in seventeen rows...]. *Tropidodipsas* Günther, 1858. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tropidodryas: G. *tropizo* (τροπιζω), furnish with a keel + G. *dryas* (δρυάς), (ref. to a nymph) inhabitant of trees. [?]. *Tropidodryas* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Tropidophis: G. *tropizo* (τροπιζω), furnish with a keel + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [...Le nom de *Tropidophis*, formé des mots grecs Τρόπις ἰδός carène, ὄφις serpent, rappellera que le nouveau genre

d'Ophidiens auquel nous l'appliquons a chacune des pièces de son écaillure relevée d'une petite saillie longitudinale..."]. *Tropidophis* Bibrón, 1840. Serpentes: Tropidophiidae.

Tropidurus: G. *tropizo* (τροπιζω), furnish with a keel + G. *oura* (οὐρά), tail. [...Kielschwanz...]. *Tropidurus* Wied, 1824. Sauria: Tropiduridae.

Tupinambis: P. *Tupinambis*, misinterpretation of the reference to the language spoken by the Tupinambá, an indigenous group from South America established on the coasts of present-day Brazil, as mentioned in Marcgravius (1648), when referring to the *teiu guaçu*, "...*Teivguacu* & *Temapara Tupinambis: Laceratus egregius*... [?]. *Tupinambis* Daudin, 1802. Sauria: Teiidae.

Typhlophis: G. *typhlos* (τυφλός), blind + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [?]. *Typhlophis* Fitzinger, 1843. Serpentes: Anomalepididae.

Uma: Apparently named after the Yuma Native American group, fide Beltz 2006. *Uma* Baird, 1858. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

Ungaliophis: L. *Ungalia*, Boidae genus now considered a synonym

of *Tropidophis* (in turn, from L. *unguis*, claw, in reference to the spur-like pericloacal structures, representing vestigial hind limbs) + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), a serpent, snake. [...Wenn nun auch die bis jetzt angenommene Diagnose des genus Ungalia in diesem Sinne erweitert werden kann und muss, so sind doch bei unserm Stück aus Guatemala die Veränderungen der Pholidose (und auch die Vermehrung der ventralia) zu ausgiebige, als dass dasselbe im genus Ungalia Platz fände...]. *Ungaliophis* Müller, 1880. Serpentes: Boidae.

Uracentron: G. *oura* (οὐρᾶ), tail + G. *centron* (κέντρον), sharp point, goad, sting. [...Les fourchettes-queue...]. *Uracentron* Kaup, 1826. Sauria: Tropiduridae.

Uranoscodon: G. *ouranos* (οὐρανός), celestial vault; by ext., mouth palate + G. *odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [... eine eigene Gattung, die zu den Iguanartigen Thieren gehört, welche Gruppe sich durch dicke, weiche Zungen, feine angefügte Zähnchen und Gaumenzähne bezeichnet...]. *Uranoscodon* Kaup, 1825. Sauria: Tropiduridae.

Urosaurus: G. *oura* (οὐρᾶ), tail + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [...tail very long and tapering, verticillate...].

Urosaurus Hallowell, 1854. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

Urostrophus: G. *oura* (οὐρᾶ), tail + G. *strophos* (στρόφος), a twisted band or cord. [...Ce nom est emprunté à deux mots grecs, qui signifient queue contournée, de Οὐρᾶ, queue, cauda, et de στρόφος contourné, *contortus*, *involutus*...]. *Urostrophus* Duméril & Bibron, 1837. Sauria: Leiosauridae.

Urotheca: G. *oura* (οὐρᾶ), tail + G. *theca* (θήκη), case, chest. [...cola tan ancha como el tronco en su nacimiento y mui poco estrechada en su extremo...]. *Urotheca* Bibron, 1843. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Uta: Named after the state of Utah, fide Beltz 2006. *Uta* Baird & Girard, 1852. Sauria: Phrynosomatidae.

Vanzosaura: P. Vanzo, apocope of the family name Vanzolini, used as a nickname + G. *saura* (σαῦρα), lizard. Honouring Paulo Emilio Vanzolini (1924-2013), Brazilian herpetologist. *Vanzosaura* Rodrigues, 1991. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Varzea: P. *várzea*, a seasonally flooded forest or wetland in the Amazon region, which is periodically inundated by river waters. [...The generic name (Varzea) is a feminine

noun, from the Portuguese *várzea* (a pre-Roman word, Iberian in origin) meaning “flooded river bank,” in allusion to the apparent preferred habitat of these species...”. *Varzea* Hedges & Conn, 2012. Sauria: Scincidae.

Virginia: SL, Virginia, a given name (fem.); also, an US American state. [?]. *Virginia* Baird & Girard, 1853. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Wilsonosaura: Wilson, a family name + G. *saura* (σαῦρα), lizard. Honouring Edward Osborne Wilson (1929-2021), US American biologist. *Wilsonosaura* Lehr, Moravec, Lundberg, Köhler, Catenazzi & Šmíd, 2019. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

Xantusia: Xántus, a family name + L. *-ia*, or G. *-ia*, suffix denoting pertaining to. Honouring Xántus János (a.k.a. John Xantus de Vesey, 1825-1894), Hungarian-born naturalist active in the United States of America. *Xantusia* Baird, 1859. Sauria: Xantusiidae.

Xenodon: G. *xenos* (ξένος), stranger, foreigner + G. *odon* (ὀδών), tooth; anything pointed. [“...*Xenos* inusitatus, et ὀδώς. H. Boie Isis 1827. p. 230...”]. *Xenodon* Boie, 1826. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Xenopholis: G. *xenos* (ξένος), stranger, foreigner + G. *pholis* (φολίς), horny scale. [“...sehr grosses Anteorbitale...”]. *Xenopholis* Peters, 1869. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Xenosaurus: G. *xenos* (ξένος), stranger, foreigner + G. *sauros* (σαῦρος), lizard. [“...Diese merkwürdige Gattung stimmt durch die Bildung der Zunge, wenn sie auch merklich flacher ist, am meisten mit den Iguanen, namentlich mit *Cyclura* überein, während die Form der Zähne und die obere Körperbekleidung mehr an die Geckonen, die Bekleidung des Bauches und des Schwanzes an die Varanen erinnert...“]. *Xenosaurus* Peters, 1861. Sauria: Xenosauridae.

Xenoxybelis: G. *xenos* (ξένος), stranger, foreigner + L. *Oxybelis*, snake genus due to Wagler, 1830. [?]. *Xenoxybelis* Machado, 1993. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Yanomamia: Y. *yanōmami thëpë*, human beings, native American culture established between nowadays Venezuela and Brazil + L. *-ia*, or G. *-ia*, suffix denoting pertaining to. [“...The generic name, feminine, is a homage to the Yanomami Indians and their lands which largely coincide with the Tepui area, the highland region of the Guiana Shield

inhabited by these lizards...”]. *Yanomamia* Machado- Pellegrino, Brunes, Souza, Laguna, Ávila-Pires, Hoogmoed & Rodrigues, 2018. Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae.

type species...”]. *Zonateres* Trevisine, Graziotin, Giraud, Sallesbery-Pinchera, Vianna & Zaher, 2022. Serpentes: Colubridae.

Zonateres: L. *zona*, encircling band/marking + L. *teres*, smooth, polished, elegant. [“...The generic epithet derives from the junction of the Latin noun “*zona*” (belt or waistband) and the adjective “*teres*” (smooth, elegant, or polished), in reference to the characteristic naked belt that separates the body and base of the hemipenis of the

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